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DECIDE FOR NEAR REAL-TIME USE OF OCEAN COLOUR DATA IN MANAGEMENT OF HARMFUL ALGAE BLOOMS

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FINAL REPORT

in co-operation with

**Plymouth Marine Laboratory
Plymouth, UK**

**Institute of Marine Research
Bergen, Norway**

EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY CONTRACT REPORT

**The work describes in this report was done
under ESA contract. Responsibility for the
contents resides in the author or organisation
that prepared it.**

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<p>ABSTRACT:</p> <p>The importance of the aquaculture industry is significant for Norway and the employment in the coastal regions. The development of the industry has over the last decades placed Norway as the world largest export nation for aquaculture fish species. The export, mainly to EU countries and Japan, was in 2000 around 371,000 tonnes of farmed salmon and trout.</p> <p>The aquaculture industry face many challenges in order to maintain profitable activities. Among the challenges are the treats from potentially natural harmful algae blooms (HAB) in the waters surrounding the aquaculture sites. In order to implement efficient mitigation actions an early warning of the possible HAB events are essential.</p> <p>The main objective of this ESA study is to identify, demonstrate and validate the benefit of using satellite Earth observation information in support of the existing decision making processes for disaster management operations. This was exemplified through the interaction with the existing management system and activities established for monitoring of harmful algae bloom in Norwegian waters in support of the aquaculture industry. The project specifically addressed the development and implementation of a pre-operational demonstration towards a sustainable service for toxic/harmful algae bloom monitoring and management decision support.</p> <p>Within the Decide-HAB project a system for making satellite EO data available for near real-time use in monitoring of HAB events in the southern Norwegian waters has been designed, implemented and demonstrated. The service has optimised for near real-time provision of information on algae bloom events, and is based on satellite data processing and analysis ocean colour data from SeaWiFS and sea surface temperature (SST) data from the AVHRR sensors.</p> <p>The project has covered the design of the technical processing, availability and interpretations of satellite EO data. Further the interaction and exchange of information with the existing HAB management structure under the authority of the Directorate of Fisheries of Norway, and under the supervision of the Institute of Marine Research has been suggested and implemented. During spring 2000 the system were evaluated and improved. The capability of the system was demonstrated, during the early detection of a HAB of <i>Chattonella</i> in the west Jutland waters off Denmark. This bloom covered large areas and partly, due to the availability of satellite EO data, only limited dedicated field investigations were initiated to monitor the development and decay of this bloom event.</p> <p>Following the definition, design and implementation phases of the project the service capabilities were fully demonstrated, during the spring algae bloom season in 2001. During this demonstration period the information from the project was used daily in the management and planning of the actions to be implemented. In March 2001 also a HAB of <i>Chattonella</i> took place in the coastal waters of southern Norway. The bloom caused a major treat to the aquaculture industry, which implied that dedicated monitoring, guidance and decision actions were initiated by the Directorate of Fisheries. The project participated in this infrastructure with daily updates of information on its web-page (http://www.nersc.no/Decide-HAB).</p>			
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1. Harmful Algae Blooms (HAB) in Norway

1.1 The Impact of HAB in Norway

Algae blooms are part of the natural annual cycle of oceanic and coastal waters. As the origin of marine primary production, algae blooms are crucial to the ocean ecosystem and to the food resources humans harvest from the oceans. Most algae species are hence not harmful or toxic to humans or the marine ecosystem, however some algae species or conditions may cause the evolution of harmful or toxic algae blooms. Up to the 1970's such harmful algae blooms (HAB) were not considered a major threat to the marine or coastal environment. Single episodic events of mussel toxicity and mortality of wild biota were recorded along the Norwegian coast, but these episodes did not attract any wide public interest or lead to any management actions. Through the 1970's several fish farms were established along the coast, however since 1980 the production of the Norwegian aquaculture industry has grown significantly from a few thousand tons to nearly 500.000 tons of salmon and trout in year 2000.

In 1981 a large harmful algae bloom (HAB) of the dinoflagellate *Gyrodinium aureolum* caused significant mortality of farmed salmon and economic losses to fish farmers (e.g. Dahl and Tangen, 1993). The bloom created much public awareness and both the fish farming industry and the authorities acknowledged that harmful algae could be a threat to activities in Norwegian coastal waters. New blooms of *Gyrodinium* followed, and during the 1980's other phytoplankton species bloomed and caused problems; *Dinophysis* spp. in 1984 (Dahl and Yndestad, 1985), *Chrysochromulina polylepis* in 1988 (Berge *et al.*, 1989; Dundas *et al.*, 1989; Johannessen *et al.*, 1989), recurrent blooms of *Prymnesium* since 1989 (Johnsen and Lein, 1989), *Chrysochromulina leadbeateri* in 1991 (Edvardsen, 1993) and *Chattonella* in 1998, 2000 and 2001 (Horstmann *et al.*, 1998; Durand *et al.*, 1999b). Of about 4,000 marine phytoplankton species, less than 300 are potentially harmful and less than 80 are toxic. However, these harmful species belong to several different algae groups (Tables 1 and 2) and consequently are notably different in terms of toxicity or damage characteristics, as well as in their eco-physiological requirements and bloom dynamic characteristics.

In early May 1998, a large harmful algae bloom dominated by the flagellate *Chattonella aff. verruculosa*, probably in combination with a small amount of *Heterosigma akashiwo*, caused mass mortality of fish in farms in the Farsund and Flekkefjord area. Around 350 tonnes of salmon died - mainly mature fish, representing a value of about 1.2 MEuro. This was the second time *Chattonella* was registered in Europe (the first bloom was registered in 1996 off the Netherlands), but the first time such a bloom appeared in high enough concentration to kill fish. The algae were later observed along the western coast of Sweden, and were observed in small to moderate concentrations in the entire area of Skagerrak by the beginning of May. Very high algae concentrations were later reported along the west and northern coast of Jutland, resulting in the death of garfish, herring and sand eel. The high concentrations of *Chattonella* in the Skagerrak and along the western coast of Jutland were found in water containing unusually high concentrations of nutrients during this period of the year. Large amounts of anthropogenic nitrate from the southern part of the North Sea together with favourable sun conditions probably stimulated this extreme algal growth. The bloom had its maximum extension during mid-May and culminated towards the end of the month. In addition, mussel poisoning incidents by the algae *Alexandrium* and *Dinophysis* were also relatively numerous in the Skagerrak in 1998. The incidence of *D. acuta* and *D. acuminata* remained high during the autumn and mussels remained toxic until the end of the year.

Figure 1 The distribution of chlorophyll during the *Chattonella* bloom in the west Jutland and Skagerrak region during May 1998. Field investigations were performed by two vessels in the period 9-19 May (left), and the pigment distribution was estimated from the SeaWiFS data of May 15 (right).

It is complex to describe the effects of this harmful *Chattonella* bloom in terms of direct financial losses. For mature salmon, losses of about 360 tonnes may be roughly 0.1% of the national export of salmon in 1998, which translates to a loss of roughly 10 million Norwegian Kroner (NOK)! Additional export losses due to damage of wild fish are not included in this estimate. However, wild fish can escape from HAB areas and their death rate may hence not easily be estimated. Further, we should note that the final effect of the bloom is compounded by the additional social and economic hardships endured by fish farmers and small and large industries dependent on fish-farming, which in the longer term may suffer job losses and reduced profits due to mass mortality of farmed and wild fish. The indirect effects of the market attitudes with respect to consumption of fish from a HAB region or country could be very significant, however these are not currently quantified. It may be reasonable to estimate that the net impact of this HAB on the Norwegian State may be on the scale of some tens of millions of NOK.

The mitigating actions possible for the aquaculture industry during a HAB situation are limited and dependent upon the nature and extent of the bloom as well as the aquaculture facility and types of farmed fish threatened. The fish may be slaughtered prematurely for use on the market, however in order to archive the best quality fish, slaughter should be performed after 3 to 12 fast-days (according to specific national regulations for food quality) in order to empty fish stomachs and to reduce fat content. An early warning will hence be of significant importance for limitation of losses. Further, enclosure pens with farmed fish may be physically towed to non-threatened waters, if the HAB threat is localised and its distribution early and well forecasted. All mitigating actions are time consuming in planning and execution, have a certain degree of risk as well as being costly. Most importantly, it is vital to warn the aquaculture industry about possible HAB in their waters as early as possible!

Table 1. Harmful algae reported along the coast of Norway in 2000, and associated potential disease: ITOX (Ichthyotoxic), MUC (inducing mucus production in gills), ASP (Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning), PSP (Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning), DSP (Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning), VSP (Venerupin) (from ALGEINFO service).

Species	Period	Affected area
PRYMNESIOPHYTES ^aAcyloxyfucoxanthins and Chl c_3 group (brown sea)		
<i>Chrysochromulina polylepis</i> (ITOX)	April-Sept.	Skagerrak, West Norway
<i>Phaeocystis</i> spp. (MUC)	March-April	N Norway
<i>Prymnesium</i> spp. (ITOX)	August	West Norway
<i>Emiliania huxleyi</i> (non-toxic)	April-August	Along Norwegian coast - offshore
DIATOMS ^bFucoxanthin and Chl c_{1+2} group (brown sea)		
<i>Chaetoceros</i> spp. (MUC)	Whole year	Coastal areas of NW Europe
<i>Pseudonitzschia</i> spp. (ASP)	April-November	SW and Mid-Norway
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i> (MUC?)	March-October	Skagerrak
SILICOFLAGELLATES ^cFucoxanthin and Chl c_2 group (yellow-brown sea)		
<i>Dictyocha speculum</i> (ITOX)	October	South Norway
RAPHIDOPHYTES ^dFucoxanthin, Violaxanthin, and Chl c_{1+2} group (brown sea)		
<i>Heterosigma akashiwo</i> (ITOX)	May	South and West Norway)
<i>Chattonella</i> cf. <i>verruculosa</i> (MUC)	May-June	South Norway
DINOFLAGELLATES ^aPeridinin and Chl c_2 group (red-brown sea)		
<i>Alexandrium excavatum</i> (PSP)	Whole year	Mid-Norway (63°N)
<i>Ceratium furca</i> (non-toxic)	Fall	W Sweden (57°N) to Mid-Norway
<i>Dinophysis</i> spp. (DSP)	Fall-winter	Skagerrak-Trondheimsfjord
<i>Prorocentrum minimum</i> (VSP)	Summer-fall	Outer Oslofjord
<i>Gonyaulax grindleyi</i>	May	South Norway
<i>Heterocapsa rotundata</i>	February-April	South Norway
<i>Polykrikos</i> spp.	August-Nov.	South & West Norway
<i>Leptocylindrus minimus</i>	June-Sept.	South & West Norway
DINOFLAGELLATES ^bAcyloxyfucoxanthins and Chl c_3 group (brown sea)		
<i>Gymnodinium galatheanum</i> (ITOX)	January, March.	Skagerrak
<i>Gyrodinium aureolum</i> (ITOX)	August-Sept.	Skagerrak and West Norway

Other minor genii: *Amphidoma*, *Heterocapsa*, *Kofooidinium*, *Polykrikos*, *Protoperidinium*, *Peridinium*, *Cerataulina*, *Coscinodiscus*, *Cylindrotheca*, *Dactyliosolen*, *Fragilairopsis*, *Guinardia*, *Lauderia*, *Halosphaera*, *Dinobryon*.

1.2 Requirements for HAB monitoring

Since the end of the 1980's, possible causes of harmful blooms of phytoplankton, as well as strategies for mitigating actions associated with harmful algae, have been a focus area for algae research and management in Norway. Management tools for tackling such problems and minimising the losses have been developed and include:

1. Careful site selection for aquaculture installations,
2. Regular monitoring of algae bloom situation and water quality near the actual sites and in the coastal waters,
3. Rapid distribution of monitoring information to the industry, public and media, and
4. Risk assessment and operational advice to the industry.

1.2.1 Development of a Norwegian monitoring service

Since 1981 a fairly regular monitoring of selected harmful algae has been developed to become operational in Norwegian waters (Dahl, 1989). Simultaneously a monitoring programme for paralytic shellfish toxins was established (Yndestad and Underdal, 1985). These monitoring and forecasting/information activities have, however, been modified and reorganised several times during the years. In the early 1990's, the Norwegian Ministry of Environment founded a national programme for ocean monitoring and forecasting (acronym HOV). HOV also included a algae monitoring and forecasting component, though the HOV program was terminated after about three years of operation.

The current hazard command chain for monitoring of HAB's in Norwegian waters is a joint public and private funded activity co-ordinated by the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries.

Regular monitoring of algae and harmful algae blooms (HABs) in Norway is conducted at 27 stations along the Norwegian coast (Figure 2) and reported to the general public through the ALGEINFO web-site (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>) administered by IMR (their research facility in Flødevigen, Norway) (Figure 3). This monitoring service is a joint effort by more than seven institutions and companies in various parts of Norway. The main objective of the monitoring program is to provide an early warning of algae blooms that may be a threat to the Norwegian marine aquaculture industry.

Regular monitoring and reporting of data at ALGEINFO is conducted once per week during the main bloom period from March to October and thereafter until winter frequency is every two weeks. During this period the probability for the development HABs along the Norwegian coast is less probable and frequent updates are not required. During emergency harmful bloom situations more frequently monitoring and information are provided. The information on algae distribution and concentrations reported in ALGEINFO is for

plankton species potentially causing HABs, as described in detail in the DeciDe-HAB Requirements document (Pettersson *et al.*, 2000a). This monitoring service is a joint effort by seven Norwegian institutions and is partly financed by the Norwegian State Food Control Authority (SNT), Directorate of Fisheries and the other participants. Sampling, identification and quantification of algae are conducted by Norwegian governmental organisations (Directorate of Fisheries, the Institute of Marine Research, the Norwegian Institute for Water Research, and the State Food Control Authority) as well as a private consultant company (OCEANOR AS).

The main objective of the monitoring program is to provide early warning of algae blooms that may be a threat to caged fish or cause toxicity in shellfish. Notably, there has been pressure from the aquaculture industry on the Ministry of Fisheries to provide increased governmental support for HAB monitoring activities. The service is mainly based on the use of *in situ* near shore observations from the participating institutions, as well as from information and measurements reported from a

Figure 2 Location of the 27 stations of regular HAB monitoring (Courtesy of E. Dahl, IMR).

number of aquaculture sites and other locations along the Norwegian coast.

The Directorate of Fisheries has implemented a contingency plan for situations of harmful or toxic algae bloom events ("*Varslingsplan for Fiskeridirektoratet ved krisehåndtering i kystsonen - Beredskapsplan 2000*" - "*Contingency plan for the Directorate of Fisheries for emergency situations in the coastal zone - 2000*". This contingency plan implies increased monitoring observations at the regular observation network, re-allocation of research vessel and other ship operations, visual airborne observations, increased ocean modelling and prediction efforts, official decision support and command lines to initiate particular precautions to limit damage, mechanisms to communicate information to fisheries, industries and export trade involved etc., as well as press and public awareness etc..

Since 1999, the ESA/ESRIN funded DeciDe-HAB project has enabled satellite earth observation (EO) data to be included in the resources available to higher level emergency monitoring efforts and the planning of field observations. However, institutional initiatives from the Nansen Center, with support from the Norwegian Space Centre, have introduced the use of satellite based sea surface temperature (ocean circulation information) during some earlier major bloom events. During the *Chattonella* sp. bloom in Danish waters in 1998, ocean colour based information was used on an *ad-hoc* research basis.

1.2.2 The ALGEINFO system

The web-based ALGEINFO monitoring system (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>) provides two main services (Figure 3):

- Information on the distribution of algae along the Norwegian coast is provided via the Internet at the regularly updated ALGEINFO web-site. The information at ALGEINFO consists of a station map (Figure 3) indicating the situation of HAB species along the coast and a short description of the situation in four major regions along the coast of Norway. There are links to useful additional information such as description of various species and their effects. If acute HAB situations should occur more frequent updating is initiated as well as direct contact to management authorities and aquaculture industry in HAB threatened areas.
- The information in ALGEINFO also provides advice on the risk of mussel toxicity, and a link is provided to the address, <http://www.snt.no/nytt/blaskjell/>. Information on this web-site is also available on a "mussel-phone" or on teletext (Norwegian Broadcasting). The basis for the advice is primarily data on the occurrence of potentially toxic phytoplankton relevant to the shellfish industry. Established levels of warning for selected toxic algae (e.g. Andersen, 1996) provide criteria for recommendations. If the levels are exceeded, the public is recommended not to consume wild mussels, and mussel producers are made aware of the fact that their stock of mussels may accumulate algae toxins.

In the past, the Institute of Marine Research has been commissioned by the Directorate of Fisheries to undertake field investigations to fulfil the tasks demanded by the emergency-response plan at all levels. IMR's activities in this respect includes redirecting of research vessels to the HAB area, sampling of environmental variables, analysis and identification of the algae species, mapping the distribution of the HABs, recording damage to fish and other marine life as well as forecasting of the development and distribution of the HAB using numerical meteorological and ocean models. 3-dimensional biogeochemical numerical ocean model, NORWECOM, at IMR is typically run in real time during critical and emergency situations and the model results are used to forecast the development and distribution of the HAB.

The role of ALGEINFO with respect to the distribution of information is instrumental, as described above. It is particularly noteworthy that in an emergency situation, ALGEINFO can represent a hub

for the rapid dissemination of support-related information. For example, forecasting of HAB development may be graphically illustrated and made available to the public and/or authorities via a link to separate web-site or web page at IMR. Further, EO data in the form of graphic and numerical presentations of actual bloom distribution is made available by internet link to the source of value-added EO-information products developed at the DeciDe-HAB project web-site (<http://www.nersc.no/Decide-HAB>).

Figure 3 The main Algeinfo web page (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>) for November 25, 1999 (detailed version in Norwegian language with summary in English, see Figure 28). The information content is provided jointly by the Institute of Marine Research (IMR), Directorate of Fisheries, Oceanor AS and NIVA. IMR Flødevigen is responsible for the weekly integration and publication.

1.2.3 The Users Requirements to Harmful Algae Bloom Information

When HABs have occurred in Norwegian waters, efforts have often been initiated in order to monitor the bloom situation, including its propagation and transport with ocean currents. This has most often involved field observations with research vessels, which provided the necessary large-scale sampling and observations. In some cases aircraft and satellite images have also been used for mapping of blooms (Dundas *et al.*, 1989; Pettersson *et al.*, 1993; Horstmann *et al.*, 1998). Propagation and transport of blooms have in some cases been recorded by continuous measurements of water movements by anchored buoys (Johnsen *et al.*, 1997), or predicted using ocean models (Durand *et al.*, 1999b).

Attempts have also been made to indicate the potential for development of large harmful blooms based on “extreme” environmental or meteorological conditions, such as high levels of nutrients (nitrate, nitrite), unusual nutrient ratios (N:P) or heavy precipitation (Dahl *et al.*, 1987). In retrospect, this has often failed primarily due to the uncertainties associated with predicting HAB development based on such parameters. *Because of this, a more reliable method of early warning of harmful algae blooms may be achieved by use of EO-based regional monitoring, and rapid dissemination of derived information.* Combined with ground truth verification and a forecast of further HAB development, such an integrated approach becomes a powerful tool for efficient monitoring. It is noted that one week's advance warning is generally considered sufficient for threatened aquaculture installations to implement mitigation activities prior to a HAB situation. However, an earlier warning may contribute to reduce the economical loss for the aquaculture industry.

The core users of the information within the Norwegian algal bloom monitoring service are the service providers and decision-makers. These users include the Directorate of Fisheries (FD), the Institute of Marine Research (IMR) and the other institutions responsible for the information made available on the ALGEINFO web-site. IMR is responsible for making an ecological assessment of HAB situations and may provide recommendations for operational responses to the bloom. However, the FD is the body that is responsible for formulating guidelines on operational responses to such HAB emergency situations and contacting the mass media. Other users of this aggregated information are the aquaculture industry itself and its affiliated organisations, such as the Fisheries Export Council etc.

The scope to the DeciDe-HAB project does not include an extensive direct end-user survey of the aquaculture industry and its affiliated organisations. The prime aim of the project is to identify and demonstrate the effect of introducing EO data in the harmful algae bloom information services mainly provided through ALGEINFO and its related organisations and authorities. Analysis of user requirements for EO based information is in this respect obtained from the main organisations responsible for public HAB monitoring activities in Norway – primarily FD and IMR. The DeciDe-HAB project activities has also been evaluated by one industrial end-user - AquaFarms Ltd., which is a co-operative representing over 25 individual fish farms. Knowledge about EO data and its potential applications is in general very limited within the current command chain for monitoring of HABs. However, through earlier demonstrations of applications of EO information, in particular ocean colour and sea surface temperature data, there is now the willingness and ability to evaluate the use of this type of information within the existing command chain. In view of this, the specific requirements for EO information are well defined and the process of identifying user requirements is achieved during the process of defining optimal use of EO information sources.

The international regulations (through e.g. FAO ESA - Agricultural and Economic Development Analysis Division and EC Directive 91/492) impose monitoring regulations for toxicity in relation to all types of shellfish harvesting. However, similar international regulations are not imposed on fish aquaculture activities since the risk of producing fish that would be harmful or toxic for

consumption due to HAB, is generally very low. Based on this the current political priorities in Norway are to develop a network for HAB monitoring to meet the requirements of the growing shellfish industry. The accuracy in identification of the type of algae species and their possible toxic effects is beyond the capabilities of at least current and near future EO sensor systems and requires analysis of water samples in the vicinity of each shellfish site (Aune et al., 1996).

Within the organisations of the current command chain and activities for HAB monitoring for the aquaculture industry in Norwegian waters the project has identified **four** major fields in which EO data can improve the HAB information provided and the decisions for actions based thereon - i.e.;

- **regular monitoring and early identification** of algae blooms within area for the current Norwegian monitoring as well as extension to surrounding "down stream" waters,
- improvement and optimization of ***in situ* sampling strategy** under regular and emergency situations,
- **EO data assimilation** for improved model prediction and forecasting of the development of identified HAB situations, and
- **multi-annual statistics** on the occurrence, extent, life time, etc. of blooms in the Norwegian and adjacent waters in order to improve scientific understanding and assessment of the causes of these blooms.

Access to and knowledge of EO data applications are limiting factors for non-expert use of satellite based information. In this respect the project has been of importance through facilitating access to EO based information through its web-site.

a) Regular monitoring, early identification and in situ sampling

The ALGEINFO monitoring program is based on sampling and analysis of water samples obtained at fixed locations and days during the regular monitoring mode of operations. During the algae growth season (from March to October) the regular sampling frequency is weekly with sampling every Monday, however at a few locations the sampling is up to three times per week. Most sampling locations are near-shore - in the vicinity of research station locations, local health authority laboratories or at selected industrial aquaculture sites. In addition the FD operates a high speed (35-40 knots) coastal patrol vessel - M/S "Munin", which performs regular weekly sampling at six fixed coastal and off-shore locations during the most critical and potential HAB periods. The vessel can operate up to 40-50 nautical miles off-shore under favourable conditions. The priorities for use of this vessel are however in competition with other fisheries patrol activities and hence the optimal use of these resources must be decided by the involved institutions. In this respect EO can provide important information for the prioritisation of the available resources for field sampling and monitoring efforts. Water samples are routinely collected in the surface (0-1 metre) and at the depth of chlorophyll maximum identified using a profiling fluorometer. The algae species composition is analysed in the laboratory and cell counts are performed. The regular analysis does not include estimation of chlorophyll concentration (Chl-a), hence a direct comparison between the satellite EO observations and the regularly monitored parameters is not currently possible. Additional net hauls are performed from open water locations at 0 to 10 metres depth in order to analyse the algae species composition.

The following key information requirements are of major concern for the fishery authorities and the aquaculture industry being influenced by HAB's:

- early warning on potential bloom development: with 2 to 11 days notification various mitigation actions can be initiated in order to save assets,
- identification and geolocation of algae blooms in the near surface and deeper layers of the water masses (usually during the autumn bloom period),

- identification and geolocation of ocean fronts and boundaries of water masses of different origin,
- localisation of thermal structures and fronts and associated water masses of different origin and
- advection, movement and interaction of water masses of different origin.

For the public HAB monitoring and advice command chain in Norway, the EO-based information is mainly needed in order to improve the early detection of possible algae blooms and subsequent planning of *in situ* observations to confirm and further monitor possible HAB situations. The current regular field observations would be optimised through tailoring of *in situ* data sampling strategies to cover gradient areas observed in the EO-based chlorophyll concentrations, homogeneous water masses of common origin, thermal front zones and identify advection of water masses towards other areas. The current sampling strategy is based on regional experiences and partly synoptic meteorological forecasts, however direct information on the ocean structures will be a new and very useful tool in planning of the sampling programme. The priorities for use of the coastal patrol vessel, in competition with other surveillance tasks, will also be better justified through use of this type of satellite based synoptic ocean information. Since field observations are required to identify definite HAB species, the absolute accuracy of the EO based chlorophyll estimates is not regarded as very critical, since relative changes in concentrations usually will indicate a change related to the algae bloom. The major application lies within the indications of changes, which then should be used to initiate other actions.

Individual aquaculture site owners (usually larger companies operating several sites) make their final decisions on mitigating actions in relation to official HAB warnings of potential threat to their own sites. The financial impact of wrong mitigation decisions is very significant, hence a high level of precision in the observed, analysed and forecasted information is essential! In this respect regional bloom information must be coupled with local knowledge of current patterns, changes in the local weather conditions etc. in order to assess the possible impact of developing bloom situation. This type of local modelling and knowledge is beyond the scope of the public ALGEINFO service, however some marine consultant companies are involved in such advisory services for individual aquaculture site owners and their insurance companies.

The aquaculture industry is becoming more interested in extending its own knowledge basis in order to optimise its profitable activities. The produced volume and economic profit margin for the aquaculture industry has increased drastically over the last decade. Coupled with reduced costs for the production of fish, this has made the aquaculture industry highly profitable, with a very prosperous outlook for the future. The perspective for expansion is that aquaculture and fisheries will become major national sectors of income for Norway in the future, so the industry itself should develop/implement a contingency plan and monitoring activities in order to be better prepared for HAB situations. The public monitoring activities are currently best placed to define and evaluate the benefit of using EO based information sources for HAB monitoring.

b) Emergency situations – model forecasting of HABs

Regular operational forecasting of the algae bloom situation is not part of current ALGEINFO activities. The reason is mainly that the knowledge basis for the initiation of blooms in the models still requires auxiliary information from external sources. Once the initial model conditions and the bloom location and species are identified, the current ocean models are able to predict the development of an identified bloom, to an acceptable level of precision. The current bio-chemical model tool (NORWECOM - Norwegian Ecological Model System) in use at IMR is based on physical forcing by the ocean circulation model run operationally by the Norwegian Meteorological Service (DNMI). The physical ocean circulation model is updated 2-3 times per 24 hours and

provides forecasts up to 48 hours of the ocean currents at a 4 km spatial resolution for the North Sea and Skagerrak region.

During the DeciDe-HAB project, EO-derived information products for initiation of a bloom situation in the model as well as for forcing and updating of the model has turned out to be very useful. Such EO based information includes sea surface temperature for physical forcing, and chlorophyll-a concentration, downwelling irradiance at the sea surface and estimate of diffuse attenuation in the water column for ecosystem forcing. The data should be provided in a form directly usable in the model, including the same grid resolution and projection etc. used in the model.

For both regular and emergency monitoring situations, FD and IMR required such EO based information updated daily or at least 3-4 times per week. In order to efficiently utilise the information, external expert evaluation and interpretations are required by both institutions.

c) Multi-annual statistics of HAB's

The public and commercial concern regarding HABs has increased over the last decades. This may partly be due to the more visible effects on the aquaculture industry as well as an actual change in the annual algae bloom cycle, including increased frequencies of HAB's and blooming of "alien" species in "new" regions (e.g. due to ship transport through disposed ballast water). In this respect the authorities (FD and IMR) need information in the changes of species compositions, dominant species and the actual algae biomass from year to year. Such average values should be acquired at typically weekly intervals, in order to resolve variability in the inter-annual timing of the bloom development. Such changes in the annual cycles may have significant negative effects on the recruitment of wild fish and other marine organisms.

Long-term monitoring of the phytoplankton situation may also be an indicator of local and regional changes in the eutrophication of the North Sea region. Several actions has been initiated in order to reduce the supply of nutrients to the North Sea, and a long term monitoring of the algae bloom pattern and the turbidity of the coastal waters, may in this respect be useful for evaluation of the effects of these actions.

This longer-term trend information is of scientific and management interest, but in the perspective of the command chain for HAB monitoring, regarded as beyond the scope of the DeciDe-HAB project.

2. The Approach of the DeciDe-HAB Project

The goal of HAB actions is *effective management of fisheries/aquaculture, public health, and ecosystem problems related to harmful algae blooms*, including specific tasks such as:

1. Improvement of *in situ* sampling strategy.
2. Development of early warning and forecasting capabilities for the occurrence and impacts of harmful marine algae blooms.
3. Development of management and mitigation strategies to minimise the impacts of harmful algae.
4. Provision for rapid response to toxic and otherwise harmful marine algae blooms.
5. Identification and improvement of access to databases for bloom incidence, toxin occurrence in shellfish, mass mortality events, and epidemiology.

In this context, the DeciDe-HAB project aimed to prototype an EO-based HAB monitoring application with public user involvement. The application would be complementary to existing monitoring activities, and would contribute to the efficiency of the ongoing HAB monitoring activities.

2.1 Contribution of EO-derived information

Earth Observation (EO) data have proved valuable for early warning of some categories of algae blooms, and through use of information about ocean fronts, eddies and gradient zones, a more efficient field sampling strategy can be implemented (task 1). A remote sensing system designed to monitor and track the formation and decay of HABs may improve an eventual forecast capability (task 2) that is necessary for the development of management and mitigation strategies (task 3) for rapid response to algae blooms (task 4). In addition, routine monitoring data required for a forecast system would provide a database containing information about the algae species, location, frequency, and duration of HAB events. These data would support studies on the impacts of HAB on the fisheries/aquaculture industries, on public health, and for basic algae and oceanographic research (task 5). Information would be displayed through the World Wide Web to allow authorities, aquaculture industry, coastal managers, research community, educators and the general public easy access to the most recent information.

In order to improve understanding of the temporal and spatial distribution of blooms and ocean front zones, remotely sensed imagery is an important source of frequent, synoptic information of the surface layer conditions. Near real-time (NRT) extraction of this information may be put to practical use in monitoring procedures for algae blooms and other oceanographic processes. In this respect EO techniques are identified to support the current command chain through:

- detection and monitoring of the distribution of photosynthetic pigment concentration, which is an estimate of phytoplankton biomass, using time-series ocean colour EO data sources;
- detection and monitoring of ocean fronts through use of sea-surface temperature (SST) imagery;
- contribute to an earlier warning of algae blooms (harmful or not) and to the understanding of the factors that influence the initiation of a bloom;
- identify, to a very limited extent, the phytoplankton categories, e.g., discrimination of coccolithophorid blooms (not harmful) from areas with other algae blooms.

Although multi-spectral Earth observation sensors can be used to detect the optical characteristics of chlorophyll *a* and other pigments that characterise algae, efforts have been constrained by the limited ability of the present sensors to discriminate phytoplankton populations at the species level. This is, of course, a fundamental requirement of a HAB monitoring program [Anderson *et al.*, 1995]. However, integrated use of EO with other sources of information on HAB species (primarily field observations) and their exact concentration will increase the value of the complementary information sources.

Due to the limited active movement of phytoplankton, most blooms are passively advected with the water masses. The main progress has been made first linking specific water masses to a bloom event, and then to identify and track these water masses with an appropriate remote sensing technique. In particular, remotely sensed sea surface temperatures (SST) have been used to follow the movement/advection of fronts, currents, water masses or other physical ocean features where phytoplankton accumulate. Pettersson *et al.* [1992] used SST data (Figure 4) from the NOAA AVHRR weather satellite to monitor the advection of the harmful *Chrysochromulina polylepis* bloom in the waters of southern Norway, in 1988 [Dundas *et al.*, 1989].

Figure 4 Time series of the AVHRR thermal infrared images during the toxic bloom of *Chrysochromulina polylepis* in Norwegian waters during May, 1988. During this event, the advection of the warm coastal water from the Skagerrak basin turned out to be coherent. The arrows indicate the position of the warm water-front [Pettersson *et al.*, 1992].

Kahru *et al* [1994] used AVHRR imagery of the Baltic to compare the total annual coverage from 1982 to 1993 and concluded that there had been an increase in abundance over time. Figure 5 shows a *cyanobacteria* bloom in the Baltic, 1 August 1999, using a SeaWiFS Rayleigh corrected colour composite (the 670, 510 and 412 nm bands as red, green and blue) and AVHRR rayleigh corrected visible (580–680 nm) band image. Similar types of EO data are also available from the ERS ATSR sensor, which has been in operation on two satellites since 1991 and is scheduled for continuation on the ENVISAT mission from 2001.

In August 1997 Orbital Sciences Corporation (OSC) launched the OrbView-2 satellite, carrying the Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (SeaWiFS). The SeaWiFS sensor was designed to measure ocean colour in eight spectral bands, covering the spectral variation of water-leaving radiance related to concentrations of phytoplankton pigments, coloured dissolved organic material, and

suspended particulate material [Hooker et al., 1992]. NASA funded the instrument development and purchased the right to use SeaWiFS data for academic research. Scientific investigators wishing to use imagery must register with NASA (<http://seawifs.gsfc.nasa.gov/SEAWIFS/LICENSE/checklist.html>). NASA licenses permit SeaWiFS data to be supplied in “near-real time” to support oceanographic research cruises for sampling of validation data. For all other research use there is a two weeks embargo on the scientific use of the data. For commercial and other regular near real-time applications SeaWiFS data are distributed on commercial terms by Orbimage Corp.

This type of visual/optical and IR satellite EO sensor typically covers a swath width of some hundred to thousand kilometres. The swath width covered is a trade-off of the spatial resolution of the data, which typically are between some hundred meters to approximately one kilometre. For SeaWiFS the swath width is 2800 km and the spatial resolution 1.1 kilometre. The orbital repeat coverage of the same location is usually several times per day, but for EO data in the visible spectral range, which are dependent on solar illumination conditions, one or two potential useful orbits per day may be available at high latitudes. Thermal infrared EO data are also applicable during night passes and typically four passes are acquired per day. These spatial and temporal scales for coverage of information are warranted because oceanographic features that initiate blooms and the blooms themselves occur at such scales. However, cloud cover and haze prevents the use of optical and infrared satellite sensors to observe the surface of the earth.

a)

Figure 5 (a) SeaWiFS Rayleigh corrected colour composite (the 670, 510 and 412 nm bands as red, green and blue) and (b) AVHRR Rayleigh corrected visible (580-680 nm) band image for 01 August 1999 showing a cyanobacteria in the eastern Baltic. Imagery processed by PML RSG and SeaWiFS imagery copyright of Orbital Imaging Corps and NASA SeaWiFS project.

2.2 The Applications of ocean colour EO data – Chlorophyll-*a* and other Pigments

The photosynthetic pigment in phytoplankton cells, chlorophyll *a*, alters the ocean colour from that of pure water. Multi-spectral ocean colour EO instruments can detect these colour changes from their orbit in space. However, deriving the chlorophyll concentration is not a straight forward task, with common validated solutions. The parameter retrieval requires complex atmospheric correction algorithms, particularly in order to retrieve with acceptable accuracy the water-leaving signal, which accounts for less than 10% of the total signal reaching the satellite sensor. Moreover, determination of the phytoplankton species and their harmfulness requires additional laboratory analysis of water samples.

According to the requirements to HAB information the most relevant EO information is related to the so-called "water quality" parameters. This includes information on the physical, biological, ecological and chemical conditions of the ocean water (Table 2). These water quality parameters are usually derived via intermediate parameters, which are directly measured by ocean-colour remote sensing instruments. Retrieval models and other *a priori* information are needed to derive water quality parameters.

Table 2: Basic physical, biological, ecological and chemical parameters observable by multi-spectral satellite earth observation sensors.

Parameters	Intermediate parameter	a priori information required
water transparency	a, b, c, K_d	hydro-optical model ⁽¹⁾ or statistically-significant correlation between an up-welling radiance ratio and K_d
water colour	R , colour co-ordinates, dominant wavelength, colour purity	hydro-optical model
Chlorophyllous pigments	a	hydro-optical model
Auxiliary pigments	a	hydro-optical model
Primary production rate	C_{chl}	vertical profiles of major optically active components, area specific primary production model parameters
Suspended sediments	C_{sm}	hydro-optical model
Dissolved organic carbon	C_y	hydro-optical model

(1): hydro-optical model is defined as *a priori* information as it is based on *a priori* knowledge of the inherent and apparent optical properties of the water.

The basic technical terms for some of the key ocean optical parameters (used in Table 2) include:

a, b, c	are the coefficients of absorption, scattering and attenuation of light by bulk water
K_d	is the coefficient of down-welling irradiance diffuse attenuation
R	is the water volume reflectance
C_{chl}, C_{sm}, C_y	are the concentrations of chlorophyll, suspended minerals and coloured dissolved organic matter (yellow substance), respectively

Atmospherically corrected SeaWiFS data provide normalised water-leaving radiance at five key wavelengths in the visible region of the spectrum. These basic measurements are used to derive products including chlorophyll *a* concentration as a phytoplankton biomass parameter (Figure 6), the diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490 nanometer (nm) as an indicator of water transparency, and water reflectance.

Advantages:

SeaWiFS images provide data with a horizontal swath width in the order of 2800 km with spatial ground resolution of 1.1 km; nominal repeat coverage of an area occurs approximately every day at high latitudes (60°).

Limitations:

- Useful data are dependent on cloud-free conditions to detect the ocean surface signal.
- Algorithms to derive phytoplankton pigments from the ocean colour signal are still a field of significant research, requiring improvements in accuracy particularly for coastal waters.
- Spatial resolution (1.1 km) of currently available sensors is too coarse for near coast and fjord observations.
- High chlorophyll *a* concentrations do not necessarily indicate a harmful bloom and currently no species-specific algorithm to determine harmful algae blooms from water-leaving radiance has been developed, however identification of Coccolithophorid blooms have been successfully performed [Pettersson *et al.*, 1995].
- Only surface layer characteristics are visible to satellite sensors, and a deeper sub-surface bloom may be hidden.

Currently, SeaWiFS has a two-week embargo on data availability that limits near-real-time access to data unless commercial prices are paid for the data.

Figure 6 Chlorophyll pigment concentration product from SeaWiFS over the North Sea and the Skagerrak, on (a) May 13, (b) May 15 and (c) May 17, 1998. © Orbital Imaging Corps and NASA SeaWiFS project. The time series shows the increases and demise of a *Chattonella spp.* bloom, along the Danish coast. Blue indicates low pigment; red indicates high pigment. Data courtesy: Remote Sensing Group, Centre for Coastal and Marine Sciences – Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

2.3 Applications of Infrared EO data - Sea surface temperature

Sea surface temperature (SST) as retrieved from satellite sensors has proved valuable for deriving important indirect information of the movement and possible extent of algae blooms. Such images exhibit dynamic features such as fronts, strong currents, upwelling zones near the shelf-edge, and other large-scale physical oceanographic features, which are related to the initiation and advection of algae blooms. The Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) sensor is used to identify physical oceanographic features through surface water temperature gradients (

, left). Other EO sensors are also available that give access to the same type of information, such as ERS-ATSR (Along Track Scanning Radiometer) and the AATSR on ENVISAT.

Microwave synthetic aperture radar (SAR) EO sensors onboard the ERS and RADARSAT satellites do not have any limitations with respect to daylight or cloud cover. These microwave sensors provide information on surface roughness (capillary waves), which under given conditions can be interpreted for information about ocean current fronts, mesoscale circulation patterns, and surface films, including biologically caused natural films (

, right). Since, these microwave EO sensors do not provide any direct information about algae bloom situation, and their use in this respect is still a topic of scientific research and their applications has not been further elaborated in the DeciDe-HAB project.

Advantages:

AVHRR data processing is highly automated and occurs in near real-time with world wide coverage of stations. Data access occurs at least four times daily and is relatively inexpensive on

a subscription basis.

Limitations:

Data are dependent on cloud-free conditions. Spatial resolution is 1.1 km and near-shore data may be questionable due to pixels affected by the signal from land. They provide only indirect information about algae blooms and other sources are needed for bloom identification and characterisation.

Figure 7 Expression of the Norwegian coastal front on October 3, 1992 in a NOAA-AVHRR image at 14:20 UTC (left) and a ERS-SAR image acquired at 21:35 UTC (right). Both images cover the same 100-km region. © ESA/NERSC.

2.4 EO applications in coupled bio-physical forecasting models

The use of coupled 3-dimensional biogeochemical and physical models in algae bloom monitoring systems is still at a research stage, and routine use of such models is not implemented operationally. However, during HAB alert events, research models in combination with regular ocean forecasting models of the meteorological service have been used to predict HAB development.

Since the algae can be considered as a “passive tracer”, a good physical model simulation the advection of the water masses will provide useful short-term transport predictions of the movement of an algae bloom. Most biogeochemical models include only a few functional groups of algae and the model developed and used by IMR, the NORwegian Ecological Model system (NORWECOM) (Aksnes *et al.*, 1995; Skogen *et al.*, 1995; Skogen and Søyland, 1998), includes two such functional algae groups - diatoms and flagellates. Most harmful algae species belong to the flagellate group and thus the modelled flagellate concentrations may be used as a proxy for the harmful algae species during HAB events. However, due to insufficient knowledge of the bloom triggering factors, the NORWECOM model (as is the case with most other numerical models of this kind) is not able to predict the occurrence in time and space of a bloom of a specific species. Thus, the

interpretation of the model predictions is strongly dependent on other observations, which can be used to initiate the occurrence and extent of the bloom in the model system. This was the case during the *Chattonella* bloom in the North Sea and Skagerrak in May 1998. During the bloom event the NORWECOM model was run in real-time and used as one of several tools, including satellite EO data, in monitoring of the bloom development and decay. The model results were very useful in combination with *in situ* observations and satellite data of the bloom region. Importantly, the model was able to forecast bloom development including the growth and movement of this large harmful algae bloom to the threatened region 48 hours into the future.

IMR performs model simulations and forecasting of algae bloom spreading and advection during emergency bloom situations, using their “Norwegian Ecological Model (NORWECOM)” tool. Due to insufficient knowledge of the mechanisms that triggers the initiation and development of algae blooms, the current model is not able to predict the initiation of new bloom developments. The forcing and interpretation of the model results is thus strongly dependent on other observations from *in situ* or EO sources to initiate the bloom situation in the model.

Integration of satellite-derived bio-physical parameters, such as sea surface temperature and chlorophyll pigment concentration, with the numerical model is a way to improve its forecasting capability. In particular, a recent study reports that even if NORWECOM was able to qualitatively reproduce the *Chattonella* bloom in 1998 [Lekve, 1998], the quantitative estimates were far from the *in situ* observations of the bloom [Durand *et al.*, 1999b].

Integration of chlorophyll *a* distribution map based on EO and *in situ* information sources, as a biological field after the physical model spin-up could constrain the model with unbiased data, and thus improve the quantification of the model variables. More advanced coupling between EO data and model can be achieved through a data assimilation scheme, which performs a dynamical and controlled adjustment of the model variable as a function of time [Evensen *et al.*, 1997].

2.5 Validation and Accuracy

Naturally EO-derived parameters need to be validated against *in situ* high-accuracy measurements used by the current service. Practical realisation of this is a scientific challenge, due to the different observation characteristics of the two types of data sources. The various algorithms developed for retrieval of in-water parameters from ocean colour data have been validated. A general summary of the quantitative achievements of EO techniques regarding the geophysical parameters of relevance of HAB monitoring is given in Table 3. The values indicated in the table correspond to the best results expected under favourable observation conditions.

In the regular ALGEMO Service, phytoplankton cell counts and algae taxonomy are adopted as suitable parameters for characterisation of (harmful) algae blooms. Both regular and dedicated cruises are carried out under the general IMR monitoring programs, for *in situ* measurements of a number of biogeochemical parameters relevant for HAB monitoring. Sampling and analysis for chlorophyll concentration depth-profiles, phytoplankton cell counts, nutrient concentration, suspended sediment, numeration and identification of algae species are performed both during these cruises and from near shore station locations. The near real-time availability of this information is however limited to certain parameters, since other parameters require further analysis in the laboratory (e.g. algae cell counts and pigment concentrations). Regular monitoring cruises are organised along the southern coast of Norway and across the Skagerrak between Norway and Denmark during the bloom period from April to July, each year. The data sets collected during these campaigns will be delivered to NERSC for use in the validation and tuning of EO-derived parameters, used in the analysis performed within this project.

Table 3. Quantitative achievements of state-of-the-art ocean-colour algorithms relevant to use in ALGELNFO. The values reported in the table result of a compilation of various algorithms, and are representative of the best achievement that can be expected for EO [revised from Durand *et al.*, 1999a].

Remotely sensed derived parameters	Algorithms			Satellite / sensor		
	Units	Range of value	Relative/ absolute accuracy	Spatial resolution (km)	Frequency of sampling (days)	Delay* (days)
Water constituents						
C_{chl} [Chl-a]	mg.m ⁻³	0.01 - 60	30 - 40 %	1.1	1	NRT
Primary production	gC.m ⁻² .d ⁻¹	0.5 - 3.0	40 %	1.1	1	NRT
C_{sm}	mg.l ⁻¹	0.1 - 30	30 - 50 %	1.1	1	NRT
C_y / a_y (380 or 440 nm)	mgC.m ⁻³	0.1 - 20	50 %	1.1	1	NRT
Optical properties						
Absorption coef.: a	m ⁻¹	all	NS	1.1	1	NRT
Scattering coef.: b	m ⁻¹	all	NS	1.1	1	NRT
Diffuse attenuation: K_d	m ⁻¹	0- 6.5	0.1	1.1	1	NRT
Turbidity/Secchi depth	m	0.25 - 5.0	50 %	1.1	1	NRT
Surface Temperature						
SST	°C	all	Rel. 0.2°C	1.1	<0.5	NRT

*Delay: Time delay of availability of products, NS: not specified, NRT: Near real-time

2.6 User involvement

DeciDe-HAB project is carried out by three main partners, as well as with the direct assistance and affiliation of the national authorities in charge of harmful algae bloom management in Norway.

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) has been the project co-ordinator, with a central role in the project of gathering and processing information delivered by the EO data provider (PML) and delivering, digested and targeted information to the user partner, the Institute of Marine Research (IMR), and to the Directorate of Fisheries (FD) as the external end-user.

The main tasks of NERSC includes;

- to analyse the products in terms of algae bloom and to deliver value-added information to the project users in intelligible and targeted forms;
- to daily maintain a project web site (including a public area) where the partners and a number of users of the service may access the NRT information on algae bloom situation;
- to collect remarks and requirements from the user side (IMR and FD) and transpose those in terms of refine products requirements, which are then submitted to PML for improvement of the EO based information products;
- to inform directly in real-time the user panel and authorities of potential HAB events; and
- to co-ordinate the overall activity of the project.

The main tasks of PML includes;

- to provide to the NERSC, SeaWiFS and AVHR-SST products adequate for HAB monitoring;

- to ensure near real-time availability of EO data;.
- to develop and adapt their current EO operational products to the specificity of the DeciDe-HAB project by incorporating requirements from the project.

The main tasks of IMR includes;

- to provide feedback on and review of the service;
- to impose constraints on additional and/or complementary information required for optimising the service;
- to eventually run their coupled physical-ecosystem model for prediction of the development and decay of a detected HAB event; and
- to gather *in situ* measurements acquired during field monitoring campaigns performed by IMR and FD, and make them available to the project for further validation and analysis of satellite images.

The main tasks of FD are;

- to provide feedback on and review of the service developed within and provided by the DeciDe-HAB project;

During the demonstration period, a panel of evaluators has assessed the service and reported to the DeciDe-HAB project. The outcome of this evaluation has helped to determine whether modifications and improvement of the system should become permanent features of the HAB monitoring activities. Only members of the panel and the DeciDe-HAB developers have had access to the demonstration web-site links via a password-protected page directory. As stated above, the linked DeciDe-HAB site should serve to distribute:

- EO information: NERSC and PML shall prepare and make available EO data / images at the official DeciDe-HAB web-site at NERSC.
- modelling information: IMR shall provide an IMR web-page for access to modelling results for harmful algae blooms;

In addition, we asked the following people to evaluate the DeciDe-HAB service. Thus, they also had access to the DeciD-HAB demonstration web-site during the period of demonstration, with the aim of receiving from them an evaluation of the system:

In Norway:

- Aqua Farms AS: Steffen Lofnes
- Directorate of Fisheries: Ragnar Sandbekk , Gunnar Larsen
- IMR: Hein Rune Skjoldal, Einar Svendsen, Einar Dahl
- Norwegian Space Centre: Guro Dahle-Strøm
- Norwegian Navy Educational Center (KNMT): Stein Otto Hole
- Norwegian Institute of Water Research (NIVA): Torbjørn Johnsen
- Norwegian State Pollution Control Authority (SFT): Per Erik Iversen

In other European countries:

- ESA-ESRIN: P. Regner, L. Fusco
- German Aerospace Research Center (DLR), Remote Sensing Technology Institute - Section Marine Remote Sensing, Germany: M. Hetscher,
- Bioconsult, AS, Denmark: P. Andersen

- Risoe National Laboratory, Denmark: Ch. Bay Hasager
- Danish Institute for Fisheries Research, Denmark: H. Thomsen
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, Sweden, B. Karlson
- Office for Environmental Protection – Fisheries Unit, Sweden: Karin Pettersson
- Ecole des Mines de Paris - Remote Sensing and Modelling Group, France: L. Wald
- as well as some other organisations and individuals, who did not actively participate during the demonstrations.

NERSC and PML organised for each person a permission to access the DeciDe-HAB web-sites and its satellite data / images including the individual authorisation from NASA for scientific use of SeaWiFS data.

At the end of the demonstration period, each evaluator provided a review of the service. A project review meeting was organised at NERSC in November 2000 to collect the evaluation information to be reporting later on in the Evaluation Document.

During the demonstration of the DeciDe-HAB element of the ALGEINFO service, interfacing with the current decision support procedure was also evaluated, including:

- ALGEINFO web-site accessibility
- DeciDe-HAB demonstration web-sites accessibility
- Quality and timeliness of the presented information
- Usefulness of and suggestions for modifications to the information presented
- Strengths and weaknesses of the service
- Recommendations for service improvements
- Suggestions for a wider dissemination strategy

In addition, a direct surveillance of the accesses made to the web-site was performed, generating statistics on number of access, origin of the access by country and type of server, etc..

3. The DeciDe-HAB System Approach

Within the DeciDe-HAB project a pre-operational system for integrated use of EO data in the existing operational HAB command chain was specified, designed and implemented. A demonstration period was carried out from the middle of April to the end of June 2000, followed by a pre-operational phase during spring 2001. Near-real time EO imagery and information have been made available on a daily basis (dependant on the cloud cover conditions) for use in the monitoring of HAB events in the waters of Norwegian interest – including the up stream Danish and Swedish waters surrounding the North Sea and Skagerrak/Kattegatt area. Value-added information products were provided for regular scientific users in support of their decision making process and field data sampling during eventual HAB situations. The services that have been developed in the frame of the DeciDe-HAB project are intimately based on the expertise of the three project partners and their interaction with the existing HAB command chain in Norway.

In this section we describe the design structure and the main products and tools for the DeciDe-HAB service support to the existing Norwegian ALGEINFO system.

The general outline of the scheme (Figure 8) adopted for the EO data implementation and the associated overall information flow, was developed in terms of four main modules:

1. EO Data provision
2. Value-adding
3. Distribution and dissemination of service products and information
4. Interaction with and within the decision support system.

Figure 8 The general information flow between the various modules of the DeciDe-HAB project.

3.1 The EO data Information Flow

A main requirement on the EO based information and service implemented under the DeciDe-HAB project was the time delay of accessibility to user friendly information products. According to the HAB user authorities a delay of up to two days from the data acquisition to the delivery of information was acceptable under regular monitoring conditions, however earlier delivery will improve the current time lag in the provision of information. Value-added and aggregated EO information products is also essential in order to match the requirements of easy use and analysis within the existing monitoring activities. The personnel involved in these operations have limited experience and time available to analyse and digest the additional information from the satellite EO data sources. Hence, easy access and availability as well as information delivery within 24 hours could bring a significant improvement of the existing system in term of its early warning capabilities for HAB events.

The success evaluation criteria for the implementation of the DeciDe–HAB project depends on four main components:

1. Availability of EO data, i.e. acquisition and transmission of the data by the satellite system; real-time pre-processing and transmission of validated information products by the receiving station to the DeciDe-HAB project team.
2. Efficiency of the system implemented within DeciDe-HAB project.
3. Appropriate definition and dissemination of the project concept, implementation and main information provided.
4. Feedback from HAB Management authorities to the DeciDe-HAB Project in terms of service evaluation and provision of *in situ* validation data.

The key elements and modules of the DeciDe-HAB service include (Figure 9):

- Provision of various EO data products through the existing UK infrastructure for near real-time satellite data acquisition at the University of Dundee.
- Value-adding processing of information products, including standard SeaWiFS and AVHRR data products, dedicated product generation and expert analysis and interpretation of integrated information from EO and other data sources.
- Service provision and information products. This part of the service has been operated in various modes according to the level of operations (regular service or the two levels of emergency HAB situations). The various products and information sources are updated regularly during the period of the services operations.
- Information dissemination and interactive contact with the decision support system (ALGEINFO). In order to assure introduction and use of value-added EO products and information the dissemination links has been based on a web-site distribution as well as direct interaction and contacts with the personnel (from IMR and FD) involved in the support system for HAB events.

Figure 9 Information flow and principal modules of the DeciDe-HAB service (red dotted area). Project actions under the responsibility of NERSC are displayed in blue, of PML in dark green and IMR's actions in salmon-pink.

3.1.1 Real-time data transmission

The DeciDe-HAB demonstration service relies on an existing operational satellite data acquisition service performed by the National Environment Research Council (NERC) funded Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (DSRS) at the University of Dundee, and the PML. The latter is a partner in the project. The ocean-colour service is based on the daily acquisition of SeaWiFS data from the US Orbview-2 satellite. The receiving station of the University of Dundee provides an operational service and real-time dissemination of various satellite based EO data to specific value-adding entities, including PML.

DSRS receives and archives SeaWiFS and AVHRR imagery over the UK and European shelf seas and north-east Atlantic Ocean. The Remote Sensing Group at the PML undertakes the data processing for the UK research user community, and for foreign customers under special agreement and contracts. SeaWiFS images are converted into level 1 HDF format while AVHRR remain in the raw HRPT format and are then transferred automatically at 2 Mbit/s over the UK academic network (SuperJANET) PML (). At PML an automated data processing system checks for the arrival of an image and starts processing usually within five minutes of pass reception. Most of the processing is automated in order to ensure an operational provision of data seven days a week and twenty-four hours a day.

3.1.2 The EO data preprocessing

a) Ocean colour processing

The ocean colour is governed by the optical properties of seawater together with suspended particles (organic and inorganic) and coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM). Phytoplankton absorb sunlight, required for photosynthesis, through pigments with 95% of the light absorbed by chlorophyll-a, b, c, photosynthetic carotenoids (PSC) and photoprotectant carotenoids (PPC) which are grouped together as the total pigments (Aiken *et al.*, 1995). As the phytoplankton concentration increases the reflectance in the blue decreases (due to the absorption of chlorophyll-like pigments over a broad wavelength band) and the green increases slightly, and a ratio of blue to green water reflectance can be used to derive quantitative estimates of pigment concentration (Clarke *et al.*, 1970). CDOM reduces the reflectance as it causes significant absorption in the ultraviolet and blue wavelengths relative to those in the red. Suspended particulate matter (SPM) enhances reflectance because of the particle backscattering that is inversely related to wavelength, is strong in the blue and then decreasing in influence through the spectrum.

The IOCCG Working Group (1998) recommended that a chlorophyll retrieval algorithm for satellite EO data should utilise wavebands at 555 or 560 nm and 443 nm and an additional waveband at 410 nm to account for CDOM absorption. SeaWiFS uses an algorithm based on the 490/555 band ratio and a cubic polynomial fit based on the SeaWiFS Bio-optical Algorithm Mini-workshop (O'Reilly *et al.*, 1998). The 490/555 ratio is used, rather than the 443/555 ratio, as it is more linear in log-log space when compared to chlorophyll-a. This is because the CDOM absorption is lower at 490 compared to 443 and there is usually a strong correlation between the chlorophyll-a and carotenoids, which are the main absorbing pigments at 490 nm, (Aiken *et al.*, 1995). The coefficients have since been updated, due to the addition of data sets, and the algorithm used at the start of the project was Ocean Chlorophyll 2 version 2 (OC2-v2), see equations 1 and 2. This was replaced by OC2-v3, see equation 3, which has additional data from chlorophyll-rich (greater than 10 mg.m⁻³) waters (O'Reilly *et al.*, 1999). In 2000 a new 4-band algorithm (OC4) was implemented in SeaDAS.

$$X = \log_{10} \frac{R_{rs}(490)}{R_{rs}(555)} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{OC2-v2 } chl = 10^{(0.2974 - 2.2429X + 0.8358X^2 - 0.0077X^3)} - 0.0929 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{OC2-v3 } chl = 10^{(0.2773 - 2.3534X + 1.1416X^2 - 0.2972X^3)} - 0.0788 \quad (3)$$

For SeaWiFS data, the processing uses a combination of the NASA SeaWiFS Data Analysis System (SeaDAS) and the SeaWiFS Automatic Processing System (SeaAPS) developed by PML (Figure 10). The average processing time for a SeaWiFS image is approximately 120 minutes (on a dual processor Sun Ultra-2), and includes placing the final products on the World Wide Web (<http://www.npm.ac.uk/rsdas>) for immediate browsing. SeaDAS is primarily designed for processing data of the so-called Case I waters (mainly open-ocean conditions), where the optical properties are dominated by phytoplankton and associated by-products. Many European coastal waters are of the so-called Case II, where the optical properties are determined by either SPM or CDOM, and frequently by a combination of SPM, CDOM and phytoplankton. SeaAPS has additional atmospheric correction algorithms, specifically designed for SPM dominated “bright pixel” waters where the near-infra red water-leaving radiance can no longer be taken as negligible and the Case I atmospheric correction (dark pixel) method fails (Moore *et al.* 1999).

Atmospherically corrected level 1 data are used to produce level-2 biological and geophysical products: water-leaving radiance at five visible wavebands (412, 443, 490, 510 and 555 nm); derived products including chlorophyll *a* concentration, Coastal Zone Color Scanner (CZCS)-type pigment concentration, diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490 nm, several atmospheric parameters determined during the atmospheric correction procedure (Moore *et al.*, 1999).

In summary, the PML SeaWiFS processing follows the following pathway (Lavender and Groom, 1999):

- Data extraction of individual bands.
- Geolocation using an orbital model and GPS data from the on-board GPS system.
- Navigation adjustment by automatic location of ‘ground control points’ to check residual navigation errors.
- Calibration of visible bands followed by calculation of water leaving radiance and biological or physical quantities, such as chlorophyll concentration or attenuation at 490nm (see section 3.2.1).
- Mapping of images to pre-selected geographical areas specified in a database with added latitude/longitude marks, annotation, temperature scale etc.
- Production of images in GIF or TIF format and storage on the WWW server.

The SeaAPS system produce both colour GIF file for easy and quick visual interpretation of algae bloom situation, as well as Black-and-white 8bits GIF files from which numerical values of chlorophyll concentration can be retrieved from further numerical analysis and evaluation.

For the DeciDe-HAB project the geographical area extended initially from 02°E to 12°E, and from 52°N to 62°N (Figure 11), and were in 2001 extended eastward to 13.5°E in order to cover the entire Kattegatt region. At this latitude the optimal SeaWiFS over-flight occurs between 11.00 AM and 14.00, with respect to the orbiting cycle. Therefore, a first analysis of daily acquisition is made available in the evening of the day of acquisition. The entire processing chain has been automated for operational purpose.

SeaWiFS Automated Processing System (SeaAPS)

Figure 10 The information flow in the PML SeaWiFS Automatic Processing System (SeaAPS) used in this DeciDe-HAB project.

b) Thermal infrared data processing

Sea Surface Temperature (SST) images are produced from Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) using the global operational equations published by NOAA (Kidwell 1995). These are based on earlier work by McClain *et al* (1985) on the split-window technique, which makes use of the difference in atmospheric absorption at two infrared wavelengths. The current formulations are called non-linear sea-surface temperature (NLSST) equations:

$$SST = aT_4 + bT_{sfc}(T_4 - T_5) + c(T_4 - T_5)(\sec sza - 1) + d$$

where T_4 and T_5 are the brightness temperatures in AVHRR channels 4 and 5, sza is the satellite zenith angle (relative to the pixel position on the Earth's surface), and T_{sfc} is a prior estimate of SST, which is taken from the simpler multi-channel sea-surface temperature (MCSST) equation. The coefficients a to d are calculated empirically by NOAA using match-ups between buoy measurements and satellite overpasses. The sensitivity of AVHRR radiometers is approximately 0.1 °C, and the published absolute accuracy of NLSST estimates is 0.6 °C root mean square difference

from *in situ* measurements.

Standard methods for calculating SST magnify the noise inherent in brightness temperature data, by multiplying the difference between channels. A modification called *partial SST*, involves splitting the standard SST equation into ‘sea’ and ‘atmosphere’ components, and smoothing only the atmosphere component (Miller *et al.*, 1997); this considerably reduces noise without blurring image structures.

AVHRR-SST data, obtained from the DSRS, are processed and “integrated” with the contemporary SeaWiFS imagery. The PANORAMA software used to process the AVHRR imagery (Miller *et al.* 1997) has been in operation for several years, with the combined ocean colour and SST products being of value to many areas of oceanographic research by providing near simultaneous observation of surface biological and physical processes. This combination acts as a precursor to data from satellites such as the European Space Agency’s ENVISAT mission, due for launch during fall 2001, which will have sensors onboard for both the ocean colour (Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer, MERIS, with 15 spectral bands and 300 m spatial resolution) and temperature (Advanced Along-Track Scanning Radiometer, AATSR). In addition also the microwave Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar (ASAR – X-band, 30 m resolution) will provide coverage within the swath of the two optical instruments.

The procedures for AVHRR processing and information retrieval are described in Miller *et al.* 1997. AVHRR data processing used follows a pathway similar to SeaWiFS with following differences:

- Geo-location using an orbital model (SGP) with NORAD two-line element ephemeris
- Calibration of infra-red bands, conversion to brightness temperature and calculation of sea-surface temperature using standard NOAA algorithms.

The data processing described above is usually completed within two hours of data reception at PML.

3.1.3 EO Data Value-adding

The GIF maps are automatically down-linked using the FTP protocol from PML to NERSC in order to disseminate the value-added information through official DeciDe-HAB web site. The EO data acquisition and automatic processing is nominally performed within less than six hours after data transmission by the satellite, allowing for analysis of the data during the evening of the day of acquisition.

A two-level analysis process has been implemented at NERSC. The first stage comprises near real-time visual analysis of the SeaWiFS level-2 data products and includes:

1. an overall evaluation of the data quality, including cloud cover detection and rejected pixels;
2. interpretation of algae bloom situation in term of chlorophyll-a pigment concentration from individual pass images and time-series of change detection;
3. in case of detection of high chlorophyll values, analysis of RGB composite and SST images in order to reduce ambiguity on the nature of the high pigment concentration (necessary in case II waters);
4. Generation of a short analysis report of the bloom situation that summarises the bloom situation as interpreted from EO and other information sources. This report also takes into account the historic development of the situations from the previous observations. The report should include identification of water masses of different origin, ocean fronts and features and the actual pigment distribution, using both SeaWiFS, AVHRR and other information sources.

5. Eventually, inform the users and the HAB command chain directly, via dedicated e-mail or telephone messages, of the detection of extensive (potentially harmful) algae blooms or other significant changes of features of importance.

A second-level analysis is undertaken in case of identified harmful algae bloom situations. This level of investigations will then include a more detailed analysis of the satellite-derived pigment concentration, synergetic analysis with other source of information (*in situ* observations, meteorological conditions, model simulations, user reports, other source of EO data, etc.). The goal of this detailed analysis is to generate an overall risk assessment map for the investigation area as well as providing direct advises for further *in situ* acquisition of information (e.g. planning of dedicated cruise activities).

3.2 The DeciDe-HAB Products and Information Dissemination

The service products depend upon the environmental situation, i.e. regular monitoring or emergency situation (algae bloom alert) efforts (see section 1.2.2).

Different types of existing and modified products have been evaluated, which are targeted toward different group of potential users, e.g. HAB information users: HAB management authorities, aquaculture industry, monitoring scientists and public media.

However, in the context of DeciDe-HAB Project and of the command-chain for decision making in management of HAB in Norway, the users of the system are primarily the Directorate of Fisheries and the Institute of Marine Research, located in both Bergen and Flødevigen. The personnel involved in HAB management at these institutions are generally scientists and/or staff with good knowledge on environmental monitoring and data sample analysis, mainly marine biologists and oceanographers.

3.2.1 EO products during regular monitoring

The regular monitoring system, the direct user access and the dissemination of the standard EO products has been performed through the dedicated DeciDe-HAB web-site established at <http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>. The WWW interface provides easy access to daily AVHRR-SST and selected SeaWiFS products, and interpretation reports of the situation related to HAB. Potential users must register with the system (via a WWW page) and their details are entered into a database, which is configured to provided access to only certain areas and products.

During the project demonstration phase, the Nansen Center performed interpretation and analysis of the EO data, and derive information products for access via the DeciDe-HAB web-site. All remote sensing products, i.e. SeaWiFS level 2 and AVHRR-SST files are split into standard Mercator-projected areas. Figure 11a shows currently active areas served by PML for multiple applications and Figure 11b the “nw” area set up to monitor Southern Norway within DeciDe-HAB. The following EO based information products has been implemented for use:

- SeaWiFS data with a nadir spatial resolution of 1.1 km and so higher resolution satellite or airborne imagery may be useful if the bloom is relatively small or close to shore. Standard level-2 products such as:
 - chlorophyll concentration (see Figure 15, left panel),
 - diffuse attenuation coefficient, and
 - project-specific products such as RGB colour composite of water leaving radiance at 443, 520 and 550 nm (see Figure 15, right panel).
- AVHRR sea surface temperature images, possibly completed with ATSR data, can provide high frequency coverage, several passes per day, when these situations occur. The analysis of SST

data gives insight on the main circulation patterns and water masses. This type of indirect information is valuable while giving additional environmental parameters to the interpretation of the current situation.

Generally, the expert analysis requires the use of information from both the AVHRR and SeaWiFS sensors. The main product is the chlorophyll-a concentration map derived from SeaWiFS using the standard NASA SeaWiFS algorithm. However, because of the inadequacy of this algorithm for case 2 coastal water, computed high values are not necessarily the mark of an algae bloom, but may be due to the presence of other optically-active substances in the water-column. The ambiguity of high chlorophyll-concentration values may, in favourable cases, be reduced by the analysis of the water-leaving radiance spectra.

Within the DeciDe-HAB project, PML provided colour composite of the water-leaving radiances at 443, 510 and 555 nm. This specific product may be of high value to discriminate algae bloom from suspended sediment, and even different family of algae (e.g. for coccolithophorid blooms).

Figure 11 (a) Currently active areas in operation by PML and (b) “nw” area set up to monitor waters of interest for Norway under the DeciDe-HAB project. In 2001 this area was slightly extended eastward to cover the Baltic inflow through Øresund.

3.2.2 Use of EO products during HAB emergency situations

During the demonstration periods of the DeciDe-HAB project two major harmful algae blooms were detected and monitored by use of integrated EO, in situ and modelling tools. These were two major blooms of *Chattonella* in respectively the west Danish (Jutland) waters in April-May 2000 and in the coastal Skagerrak waters during March-April 2001.

During emergency bloom situations of *Chattonella* the project ran a regular operational monitoring mode delivering daily images (or as frequent as they were useful/cloud free). This information was supplemented by additional data sets, which came from other environmental observations and/or model sources. Auxiliary to the project information from dedicated ship observations/cruises and airborne reconnaissance, including visual observations, were also initiated by the Directorate of Fisheries. The Nansen Center and IMR participated in the day to day advisory efforts with up-dates

of the satellite EO information and model forecasts.

During emergency bloom situations, IMR also performed real-time model simulations and forecasting of algae bloom development, using their combined physical ocean and marine ecosystem model (NORWECOM). For the 1998 HAB event, the model was able to forecast bloom development including the growth and movement of this large harmful algae bloom in the threatened region, up to 48 hours into the future. However, due to insufficient knowledge of the mechanisms that triggers the initiation and development of blooms, NORWECOM (as is the case with most other numerical models of this kind) is not able to predict the occurrence of a new bloom of a specific species. The interpretation of the model results is thus strongly dependent on other observations from *in situ* or EO sources to identify blooming situations.

Integration of satellite-derived bio-physical parameters, such as sea surface temperature and chlorophyll pigment concentration, with the numerical model is a way to improve the forecasting capability. Specific integrated EO information products must then be elaborate for integration within the model. In particular, DeciDe-HAB enabled the delivery of derived chlorophyll distribution at model grid scale and projection. Since EO data have a much better resolution (about 1 km at nadir) than the model (20 km), optimal data smoothing may be undertaken.

3.2.3 Evaluation, interpretation and analysis

The region of the DeciDe-HAB monitoring has been geographically divided into seven sub-regions: Kattegatt, East Skagerrak, West Skagerrak, West Jutland, Hordaland, North Sea, and south-west Norway (Figure 12). For each zone, a brief description of the algae bloom situation is given, taking into account the information gained from the images of the day, as well as the recent history of processes and events in the area and the information from *in situ* field data and observations.

Figure 12 Geographical sectors of the project area in which a simplified colour code is used to characterise the algae bloom situation.

The daily analysis required SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a concentration maps complemented by the analysis of water-leaving radiance spectra in order to reduce the false-alarm rate in case II waters.

The analysis of SST data provided information about the main ocean circulation pattern and the water masses of various origin. In case of regular monitoring, conclusions of the analysis of the various EO and non-EO data sources are also provided in a short descriptive text, which in wording summarises the bloom situation in the region and facilitate the own interpretation of the non-experts.

3.2.4 The User Interface

The DeciDe-HAB project implemented a web-based browser system for the dissemination of information on algae bloom situation in near real-time (typically four to ten hours after the acquisition of the satellite data).

The web-site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>) is the main user interface to the information provided by the DeciDe-HAB service. In case of detection of potential harmful bloom events active and direct communication initialised, following the structure implemented in the national contingency plan for handling of emergency situations in the coastal zone (Anon., 2000, see Section 1.2.2).

The web-site includes five main areas, which can be access through the web-site front-page (Figure 13), some areas have open availability and some are password protected and available for project accredited users:

- The general project description area, including the project objectives, partnership, promotional information, press releases, project funding, etc. (Figure 13).
- The public daily information on oceanographic situation in the monitored area (Figure 14). This information includes selected AVHRR-SST images of the day and a short text analysis of the situation, based on all available information. A link to the SST image time series archive is implemented, as well as a link to the SeaWiFS daily report page (restricted access).
- The project-restricted area for daily information on the algae bloom situation (Figure 15). The daily updated web-page includes a selection of SeaWiFS image products relevant for algae bloom analysis, i.e., chlorophyll-a concentration and RGB colour composite of water-leaving radiances. A report analysis of the bloom situation is included in text format. Information on previous situations can be browsed through a link to the SeaWiFS image archive organised in monthly batches. A java-script allows the user to navigate the images and point out geographic locations and feature of interest, including the actual value of the concentration parameters within the image (Figure 16).
- The project-restricted area for archive, time series and dynamical analysis of bloom events (Figure 17). The archive area gives access to daily AVHRR-SST, and SeaWiFS chlorophyll and RGB images acquired during the project period (March to July, 2001) and for the three last years (1998 to 2000). A system of graphical links through an intuitive design allows the user to navigate through the time series of products (Figure 18), and then to retrieve the information pertaining to a specific day (Figure 15).
- The modelling area (Figure 19) gathers the main results of simulations and prediction of HAB development, performed by IMR using the 3-D coupled physical-ecosystem model for the North Sea region (NORWECOM).

- HOME
- About DeciDe
- Objectives
- Deliverables
- Data browser
- Tutorial
- Links

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Welcome to the home page of

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Latest Updated Situation (daily information)

Highlight of the season 2001

Hot Topic
Press Release (in Norwegian)

Numerical Simulation & Forecasting

ALGEINFO

The direct link to the official Harmful Algae Bloom Monitoring service of Norway

This research project is sponsored by
the [European Space Agency](#) and the [Norwegian Space Centre](#)
co-ordinated by the [Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center](#)
Project coordinator: [Lasse H. Petterson, NERSC](#), Bergen, Norway.

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Last modified: Mon Aug 13 14:21:35 MET DST 2001 by [Dominique Durand](#).

Figure 13 Home page of the DeciDe-HAB web-site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>).

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

Decide-HAB is a R&D demonstration project with objective to improve near real-time collection of field observations of Harmful Algae Blooms (HAB) in Norwegian and neighbouring waters.
The below satellite image (NOAA AVHRR) shows the Sea Surface Temperature (SST) information, indicating the different water masses present in the region.

Tuesday, 05 July 2001 - NEW! HAB info
 Sea Surface Temperature

<p style="text-align: center; font-weight: bold;">Afternoon image Time: 1238</p>	<p>Evaluation of the situation as of: 05/07/2001 Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N Longitude range : 2.0 13.5 W</p> <p>Comments :</p> <p style="color: red; font-size: small;">Warm water from the Baltic are moving Northwards along the Norwegian coast. The front is actually located at Lista fjorden.</p> <p style="color: red; font-size: small;">An intense eddy-circulation structure is developing in the center Skagerrak and Northwards off the coast of Norway, and until Stavanger.</p> <p style="color: red; font-size: small;">See for more information (restricted access - mail to the Nansen Center to get a password).</p>	
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click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

[Earlier Situation](#)

[Enter Decide-HAB restricted area](#)

Part of the satellite information provided through the project is restricted, due to Copyright regulations.

A temporary access can be granted to people involved in HAB-monitoring and field data collection.

Contact [Dominique Durand](#) to get a password. Please give a short description of your main motivations for accessing this site.

The authorization access to this site can be changed without notification.

Figure 14 The public area displaying daily AVHRR-SST images and a short descriptive analysis of the water masses identified in the region and their possible advection from previous observations, as well as the algae blooming situation.

Figure 15 Restricted-to-project web-area, displaying daily SeaWiFS level 2 products (chlorophyll concentration on the left and reflectance RGB composite on the right), and descriptive analysis report of the algae bloom situation.

Figure 16 Interactive navigation and image processing interface (java-script) implemented for the Chlorophyll and SST images on the project site since 2001.

Figure 17 The data browser overview to time-series archive of SeaWiFS and AVHRR-SST products.

Browsing: /SeaWiFS/2000/May

All SeaWiFS images and data presented on this website are for *research and education* use only.

All commercial use of SeaWiFS data must be coordinated with [ORBIMAGE](#).

← [Parent] [1998] [1999] [Previous] [Next] [Today] [SST Archive]

SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a products - May 2000

Click on the image for A4 size

Figure 18 Example time series of maps of SeaWiFS-derived chlorophyll concentration for the month of May 1998, as available through the restricted area of the DeciDe-HAB web-site. Each image gives direct access back to the daily images and report from the various days.

Figure 19 The model results web-area displays of simulations and forecasting of the development of identified HAB events. The upper time series shows the growth and decay of the *Chattonella* bloom (concentration of flagellate in $\text{mg N}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) between April 12 and May 16, as predicted by the NORWECOM models. The model was initiated by the SeaWiFS-derived chlorophyll concentration, as observed in the image of April 19. The lower time-series shows the predicted decay of nitrate between the same period of time, producing a limitation in nutrient supply and hence the decay of the bloom. Information and modelling results of this kind is only made available in case of identified HAB situations, i.e. under the various higher levels of alert situations.

Figure 14 shows the web-page, which displays the daily AVHRR-SST images graphically to the user and gives an indication of the cloud cover (percentage of valid pixels). The user can then navigate into the SeaWiFS link and enter the project restricted area (Figure 15), which displays the appropriate ocean colour based products and the information resulting from the analysis of the HAB

situation. Within both the AVHRR-SST viewer and SeaWiFS viewer, the user can access the time series for the current year by following the link to the browser archive (Figure 17). There the user can navigate through the images by going to specific dates or using the previous/next buttons if a time-series of image products is to be investigated (Figure 18).

3.3 Project Interactions with the Existing Service

The role of ALGEINFO with respect to the distribution of information is instrumental. It is particularly noteworthy that in an emergency situation, ALGEINFO represents a hub for the rapid dissemination of support-related information. For example, EO products and derived information in the form of graphic, numerical and text presentations of actual bloom distribution is made available by Internet link to DeciDe-HAB web-site at NERSC. Furthermore, forecasting of HAB development may be graphically illustrated and made available to the public and/or authorities via a link to separate web-site at IMR and/or NERSC.

The ALGEINFO web-site has a link to the DeciDe-HAB project web site at NERSC, as well as to another IMR server (in Bergen) to access views of model simulations of the development of harmful algae blooms. Thus, end users of the web-site may view actual EO images of algae bloom development and prognoses of the extent and development of identified HAB event.

The Directorate of Fisheries in Norway has the primary responsibility for monitoring harmful algae blooms and providing warning and advice during HABs along the Norwegian coast. The Directorate of Fisheries has developed an emergency-response plan (Anon., 2000) with three-level action according to the HAB situation. The plan defines operational responses and lines of command and communication (on internal, national and international levels, and to the marine aquaculture industry, fisheries authorities, the press, etc.), for each level of response.

Primary contact persons for the DeciDe-HAB project at the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries have been:

- Ragnar Sandbekk, Chief Officer, responsible for the contingency plan for the coastal zone.
- Gunnar Larsen, advisor, Regional Fisheries Office, Fredrikstad.

The Institute of Marine Research, although responsible for monitoring the algae situation in the shelf and open-ocean waters, is not the responsible organisation for coastal monitoring of HABs in Norway. The IMR role is on the data acquisition and analysis supporting the management during identified HAB situations. This role may be in the form of special cruises to HAB areas, modelling of the HAB development and transport, and other supporting actions. At the Institute of Marine Research, specific contact persons are to be notified during HAB situations. These persons are:

Primary contact at IMR:

- Hein Rune Skjoldal, Science Director, Division of Marine Environment, Bergen

Secondary contacts at IMR:

- Jan Aure, Senior Researcher (monitoring, physical oceanographer), Division of Marine Environment, Bergen
- Einar Dahl, Senior Researcher (phytoplanktologist), Research Facility in Flødevigen.
- Francisco Rey, Senior Researcher (phytoplanktologist), Division of Marine Environment, Bergen

Interfacing between IMR and the Fisheries Directorate has usually been good in the past, although room for improvement in the speed of communication and dissemination of information exists.

4. Service Demonstration

4.1 HAB Events and Monitoring

Both in the spring of 2000 and 2001 extensive harmful algae blooms were observed in the geographical area monitored by the ESA DeciDe-HAB project. The bloom timing and extent were however quite different, as were the monitoring responses initiated by the Directorate of Fisheries.

Late in April 2000 an extensive algal bloom was detected by the project team in the satellite images in the area west of Denmark (Jutland) (Figure 20 and Figure 21). *In situ* observations confirmed that the algae bloom consisted mainly of *Chattonella* spp. It was feared that the bloom would follow the prevailing cyclonic circulation through the Skagerrak region and eventually affect the fish farms along the coast of southern Norway. At the Institute of Marine Research the NORWECOM model was initialised and predictions of the behaviour of the bloom were produced (Figure 22). The Directorate of Fisheries received the information from the DeciDe-HAB project based on satellite imagery and modelling, but the bloom was not considered an emergency situation. Dedicated *in situ* sampling for algae analysis was carried out, but based on the information from the DeciDe-HAB project it did not initiate any emergency measures, however the situation was carefully monitored. The modelling results showed that it was unlikely that the bloom would reach the fish farms on the Norwegian coast and the satellite imagery also showed that the bloom remained on the western coast of Denmark. Thus the information from the DeciDe-HAB project obviated establishment of an emergency situation with extensive dedicated *in situ* sampling and analysis. During a similar bloom event in May 1998 in the same area dedicated field observations were initiated using two research vessels and causing additional costs for the field data sampling and analysis amounting to about NOK 600.000.

Figure 20 The growth of the *Chattonella* bloom west of Jutland, Denmark, during April, 2000. Images are from respectively 18., 20., 29. April and 4. May. The high pigment concentrations due to the *Chattonella* bloom are indicated in red. Cloud cover and land is in black.

Figure 21 The decay period of the *Chattonella* bloom west of Jutland, Denmark during May 2000. Images are from respectively 7 – 10 May.

Figure 22 Comparison of the SeaWiFS based chlorophyll pigment distribution (in mg chlorophyll/m³) and the flagellate concentrations as resolved in the NORWECOM model (in mg Carbon/m³, range 0-250 mgC/m³) for respectively 18. April, 8. and 16. May, 2000 during the *Chattonella* bloom west of Jutland and in Skagerrak.

The *Chattonella* bloom in the spring of 2001 was quite different. The bloom was first detected through loss of fish in fish farms on the south-east coast of Norway on March 16. The Directorate of Fisheries then contacted the Nansen Center and the DeciDe-HAB project service was made fully operational with daily

updates of satellite imagery on the project web-site (Figure 23). Already prior to this the site was functioning automatically with image updates: however no daily analysis had yet started. Analysis of daily images and retrospective data was very useful in the first assessment and overview of bloom extent as well as the later monitoring of the extent and development. At the Institute of Marine Research, NORWECOM, was initiated and predictions of the development of the algae bloom were produced. An emergency monitoring and advisory group was established by FD. This group had daily meetings to co-ordinate the field data sampling and prepare advice and public information dissemination. Staff from the Nansen Center and IMR participated in daily steering and advisory meetings and the DeciDe-HAB project provided valuable information on the extent and development of the algae bloom, based on satellite information and images as well as model predictions. This information was of great value in the daily planning of emergency and mitigation measures as well as defining *in situ* data sampling strategy.

Figure 23 The growth of the *Chattonella* bloom in March, 2001 as observed in the pigment concentrations derived from the SeaWiFS data from respectively 20., 21., 23. and 25. March. Land and clouds are indicated in black and red high pigment concentrations.

These two HAB events illustrates clearly the important roles that EO information can play in the algae monitoring. In the spring of 2000 the satellite images provided an early warning of the bloom, and together with modelling the imagery was used to monitor a situation that had the potential to become a more critical emergency situation. Partially based on the available EO information it was decided to not establish an emergency group at FD, with the resources and cost implications of such initiatives. In this respect resources and money for monitoring efforts was saved.

In 2001 the EO was not able to give an early warning and the bloom was first detected through loss of fish in fish farms. The situation in 2001 was exceptional compared to earlier harmful algae blooms. The bloom caused problems in mid March as compared to earlier spring blooms that have occurred in late April and May. Thus even if a bloom was detected at that early stage it would not have expected to be harmful. The EO information and modelling results, however, proved to be valuable in the handling of the emergency situation and illustrates that this type information often can provide valuable information to complement the monitoring of algae, possibly harmful, blooms (hereafter (H)AB) events.

Based on the demonstrations provided by the Nansen Center and later the DeciDe-HAB project the Directorate of Fisheries view the satellite EO imagery and the modelling results received as an essential part of the monitoring and emergency handling of algae blooms in coastal Norwegian waters. In the past (in 1998 and 1999) the “service” has been provided on good will from institutions (Nansen Center, PML, IMR), and lately (in 2000 and 2001) by the DeciDe-HAB demonstration project. The Directorate of Fisheries has taken steps toward the Ministry of Fishery to establish a service of this type on a permanent basis, but funds are not yet available to establish a more permanent access to EO based information in the monitoring of (H)AB events in waters of Norwegian interest. The political debate concerning the future of the aquaculture industry has been raised lately in Norway and includes the fact that this industry is a very profitable activity. The debate centre on whether the responsibility for such algae monitoring actions should be funded by the industry itself instead of governmental resources as to a large extent is the situation to day.

4.2 Summary of Service Capabilities

We give hereafter a synoptic summary of the maturity and current status of the support service as by the end of the DeciDe-HAB project. Data flow and technology adopted for the current service are presented in Figure 24. A similar table is given in section 6 concerning ways to further develop the service and to overcome the major service limitations discussed in section 5.

Table 4. Current status of the DeciDe-HAB service

Service component	Status and Performance
Products	
Information content	Maps of sea surface temperature and chlorophyll-a concentration from r4spective AVHRR and SeaWiFS imagery. Additional derived products (RGB ocean colour composite, Diffuse attenuation – K490) may be used to help in interpreting algal bloom events and ocean surface features. Daily report on algal bloom events based on analysis of time series of satellite data and possibly additional <i>in situ</i> information (currents, wind, <i>in situ</i> measurements of chlorophyll concentration and cell count.
Accuracy	SST maps accuracy: 0.5 °C Chlorophyll-a maps: 30 to 100 % depending on applied algorithm and ecosystem status.
Algorithms	SST maps split-window method. Chlorophyll-a maps in near real-time: black pixel assumption for atmospheric correction and NASA OC-2 algorithm for in-water processing. Re-analysed chlorophyll-a maps: Atmospheric correction: either black pixel assumption with iterative approach for determination of aerosol parameter or bright pixel assumption (MUMM algorithm – Ruddick <i>et al.</i> , 2000) In-water processing: OC-2 algorithm or Levenberg-Marquardt inverse approach.
Functioning	
Availability	Access to SST maps and short report opened to anyone Access to SeaWiFS-derived products and detailed analysis restricted to NASA authorised SeaWiFS data users. In case of identified risk, direct contact with authorities through phone, fax and/or email.
Timeliness	The service has proven timely with regards to the <i>Chattonella</i> blooms in 2000 and 2001.
Reliability	<i>Identification of new algal bloom event:</i> The DeciDe-HAB system has proven to be quite reliable for identifying high-biomass algal bloom. Although no information is provided on the possible harmfulness of the bloom, and limited accuracy on algal concentration is obtained.

	<i>Monitoring of identified bloom and HAB:</i> efficient monitoring of the development, propagation and decay of bloom has been demonstrated.
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Table 4 follow-on	
Service component	Status and Performance
Supply chain	
Distribution performance	Information is provided on a daily basis. A delay of 6-hr or better is routinely ensured between data acquisition and information provision on the web site.
Automation level	The entire acquisition and processing chain and web-site updating are automated. Analysis may be performed online using image visualisation and navigation tools available through the web-site. Reporting may be performed online through the web-site by authorised persons.
Packaging of information	Daily information is provided through two main web-pages for SST and SeaWiFS-derived maps respectively. Links to additional information, such as outputs of model simulation and forecasting is provided when appropriate and/or available.
Benefit	
Cost effectiveness	So far, cost effectiveness has been ensured by free-of-charge provision of satellite data to the project. Service operation and maintenance requires a half-time appointment. The level of automation that has been reached, ensure now the work to be focused on analysis and information provision, instead of administration and web-site development routines
Competitiveness	The service has no competitors in its category (remote sensing based information provision), A number of other HAB-related “services” and information suppliers exists indeed. The information provided is either based on <i>in situ</i> sampling, ship-of-opportunity, remote sensing or modelling. However none of them has up to now reached the level of DeciDe-HAB in terms of automation and near real-time access to the information.
Customer readiness	
Awareness	The DeciDe-HAB service has received a good echo in the local and national press with a couple of articles published during the <i>Chattonella</i> bloom in March 2001. The project was first restricted to Norwegian authorities in charge of HAB monitoring (Directorate of Fisheries and Institute of Marine Research). The restricted area is now accessible to twenty operational and science users originated from 6 European counties. The web-site receives 10 daily connections in average, with peaks to more than 200 connections during HAB events.
Acceptance	Based on the demonstrations provided by the DeciDe-HAB project the Directorate of Fisheries view the satellite EO imagery and the modelling results received as an essential part of the monitoring and emergency handling of algae blooms in coastal Norwegian waters. Since NERSC takes part of the daily steering and advisory meetings during crisis monitoring.
Practices	Registered users seeks for information on the web site every two weeks in period of regular monitoring and in average every two days during HAB events.
Customers	National Authorities in charge of HAB monitoring, Research centers in environmental study, Civil-engineer school, Defence Department, Space Centers.

Figure 24 Data flow and technology adopted in the frame of the implementation of the DeciDe-HAB service.

5. Problems areas and constraints for further development

5.1 *Scientific and technical constraints and limitations*

In general there is a wide range of issues which remains to be solved in the use of satellite based ocean colour data for retrieval of water quality parameters including the chlorophyll a concentration. These general issues relates to the sensor limitations (e.g. cloud cover and seasonal daylight availability), atmospheric correction algorithms (e.g. their validity and accuracy, and access to ancillary information) and the pigment retrieval algorithms (e.g. their accuracy and validity in different water systems). A number of these general scientific limitations remain to be solved or improved for a better general use of ocean colour data from space platforms. Such improvements will of course also benefit the applications demonstrated in this project too. However, in this section we address some of the specific limitations and problems related to the current use of EO data in HAB monitoring.

5.1.1 What kind of bloom are we able to detect and monitor?

Cloud cover limits use of ocean colour data from satellites. However, in some cases extensive algae blooms are also co-incident with enhanced solar radiation and hence less cloud cover. Integration of data from consecutive days may overcome limitations with cloud cover.

Ocean colour sensors provides only information about to the upper part of the water column, typically <10m depending on the actual water transparency. Because of this, EO technology can only provide information on surface blooms and sub-surface blooms might be hidden in the deeper waters. Satellite imagery is of special help with massive blooms of possibly harmful algae species, especially the ones associated with frequent “sunny days”. Some of the blooms that occur later in the year are often characterised by a subsurface chlorophyll maximum and are hence not usually detectable from satellite observations. Satellite imagery is also of no or limited help in the monitoring of nuisance algae that may cause shellfish poisoning. Shell fish poisoning problems often occur with algae that have a low abundance and the highest concentration of the toxic algae may occur at depth and neither the concentration nor the location of the bloom makes them observable from satellite. Therefore, use of ocean colour EO data is limited to some types of algae blooms and hydrological situations. However, when applicable the ocean colour data provides a very good overview of the bloom extent.

Another limitation from ocean colour EO data is the capability to discriminate between algal species. Basically, present technology (sensor sensitivity, number of spectral band, signal-to-noise ratio, and retrieval algorithms) only allows discrimination of mono-specific blooms of coccolithophorids from other algae species, because of their very specific spectral signature, *i.e.* high reflectance over the entire visible spectrum due to high reflection on calcareous coccoliths. Research is underway to try to identify not only the spectral signal contribution from the chlorophyll pigment, but also other types of photosynthetic pigment (phycoerythrin, phycoxanthin, etc.), which are specific of certain families or groups of algae. New EO sensors, such as MODIS and MERIS, will provide a larger number of spectral bands, and may contribute in achieving this goal. Preliminary retrieval algorithms have already been presented for the quantification of phycoerythrin, however these algorithms are still at a research level. We may expect to see operational algorithms of this type within the next five years.

Further limitations of EO data are related to the qualification and quantification of harmfulness due to an algae bloom. There is no possibility that the toxicity/harmfulness of algae might be identified

or measured by satellite observations. Likewise, there is very little chance that EO technology might some day give access to the identification of an alga at the Genus level. Nevertheless, a breakthrough would be achieved by the identification of the family of the dominant algae (if applicable) in a bloom. However, through integrated use of information from EO sources, regional and seasonal knowledge and *in situ* data sampling, this kind of detailed bloom identification information might be provided.

On the other hand, we have proven through the DeciDe-HAB project that the monitoring of an identified bloom can be efficiently carried out using EO data as an integrated part of the near real time analysis and assessment of the algae bloom situation.

5.1.2 Bloom Triggering Factors

Marine algae growth in general is governed by the annual cycles of the oceans, however regional variations in the biological (availability of a specific specie), chemical (nutrients etc.) and physical (temperature, salinity etc.) conditions might be triggering factors for a specific algae bloom. If a bloom is toxic or harmful depends on the specific species or the actual concentration of the bloom.

A (harmful) algae bloom may occur in a matter of days, and may disappear just as rapidly, and may be geographically limited or extend over huge areas. Blooms generally mark a convergence of factors that encourage phytoplankton growth. These factors can be anthropogenic or natural, including: introduction through de-ballasting of large boats or transportation of living shellfish; or an algae specie present in a “favourable” environment defined by available sunlight, amount and composition of the nutrients, water temperature and hydrodynamics. Various species have different optimal growth conditions, related to nutrients etc., which may set an “hierarchical organisation” or succession of blooms during the growth seasons. In addition, the biological cycle of the individual algae species, and the prey/predator conditions, influence the bloom development and decay conditions. All factors that determine the intensity and biological cycle of a bloom are complex and still not fully understood. Currents and advection of water masses are essential for the spatial distribution pattern of bloom event. Mechanisms that contribute to the termination of a bloom includes hydrodynamical and wind-driven transport and vertical mixing as well as the opposite of the bloom triggering factors mentioned above - lack of nutrients, reduction in solar radiation and water temperature to a certain extent.

A general understanding of the processes that lead to HAB events can only be reached through the analysis of integrated “trans-boundary” data sets. In the Baltic Sea, the Skagerrak, the coast of Norway and the eastern North Sea, specific actions are carried out to monitor and rapidly inform the authorities and public on potentially HAB events. Frequent coastal sampling, using research ships and helicopters, ships-of-opportunity, satellite EO data, and visual observations by e.g. coast guard pilots are used to provide information about the bloom situation. Toxicity tests are carried out with varying intensity, based on sampled water and expert laboratory analysis.

5.1.3 EO Retrieval algorithms for Case II water and shallow water

Most harmful blooms of concern are generally those which reach the coastal and near shore waters, since they have the largest potential impact on human activities and health.

The most useful algae bloom parameter derived from ocean colour sensor is the chlorophyll pigment concentration (CHL), which is directly related to the intensity of the bloom. Most of the algorithms implemented for the retrieval of chlorophyll concentration from ocean colour data are based on empirical models that are tuned for Case I waters, i.e. chlorophyll-dominated waters. Generally these algorithms are not optimal for use in coastal waters, in which several optically

active components contributing to the spectral signal measured by the EO sensor. The problem may become even more complex when moving to shallow-water areas, close to the shoreline. These empirical models are based either on world-wide open ocean data sets or local data sets that are only representative of a specific region. The main issue is the accuracy of the chlorophyll concentration retrieved. The residual signal contribution from other optically active components varies with the types and concentrations of compounds present in a specific area, so both seasonal and geographical variability occurs. Therefore, it is difficult to *a priori* predict the accuracy that could be obtained by using one of these models in a region like the DeciDe-HAB area. Nevertheless, it is found that the global processing algorithms provide useful information related to the early detection and monitoring of development and decay of (H)AB events as observed during the project.

The critical range of chlorophyll concentrations relevant to HAB is within the validity of the current EO capabilities. The algorithms overflow/saturate when the chlorophyll concentration is higher than about $60 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, however during such conditions the level of accuracy is not critical since the situation is treated as a high concentration algae bloom.

The presence of other optically active compounds, such as sediments and CDOM, in the water column reduces the reliability of the EO detection algae blooms. However, it is anticipated that use and interpretation of several ocean colour derived products, may help in overcoming this limitation. In this respect the signal contribution and error introduced is significantly dependent on the location and time of the year. Early spring blooms, prior to the initiation of snow melting and increased river run-off may be less affected than waters interacting with the river plumes during the melting season.

Present EO capability may not cover the entire range of possible CHL values in case of algae bloom, and do not give the capability to detect and predict the occurrence of blooms of a particular algae species. Nevertheless, satellite data is certainly valuable for detecting those blooms that are characterised by a rapid and significant increase in phytoplankton biomass. However, for monitoring of low concentration highly toxic algae blooms, both models and EO observation technologies are of limited value.

Recently significant research efforts have been undertaken within atmospheric correction and retrieval algorithms for Case II waters. Solutions are mathematically more complex, often more compute intensive. Therefore, performance regarding operational applications must be assessed. Most of these new methods are based on inverse techniques, and involve the retrieval of all optically active components simultaneously. They generally require large amounts of *in situ* measurements in order to calibrate and validate the algorithms. For early warning and monitoring of HAB events the increased accuracy in the retrieved parameters needs to be balanced against the complexity and computer resources needed for the operational use of these new methods. In most cases one can undertake a service with less accurate information and still detect the most important algae blooms and their further monitoring.

5.1.4 Limitations of modelling and prediction capability

Although a great deal is known about the ecology and physiology of harmful algae, major gaps still exist in our understanding of the factors controlling the population dynamics, including initiation, of HAB. For these reasons it is of fundamental importance:

- to reach a better understanding on the environmental conditions and assemblage properties of specific HAB events, and
- to improve our capability to model and further simulate the initiation, development and decay of HAB events.

Earth observation technology and numerical modelling are valuable for the early detection, monitoring and prediction of high-biomass and geographically extended (H)AB. Optimal integration of these technologies and information sources has not yet been fully exploited. The European Initiative on HAB (EUROHAB) stated that this needs not only the development of 3-dimensional (3-D) hydrodynamic models of the areas subject to HAB outbreaks, but also the incorporation of biological components into those hydrodynamic models, i.e. integrated ecosystem models like NORWECOM. Research and development models presently exist but have not yet been used specifically for simulation of scenarios related to various anthropogenic impacts on ecosystems under HAB influence. 3-D models have been used successfully to forecast the development and decay of cyanobacterial blooms in the Gulf of Finland and flagellate blooms in the Skagerrak region.

It is not only the phytoplankton physiological characteristics that determine harmful algal blooms. Hydrodynamics and grazing are also important factors controlling the formation and decay of many phytoplankton species. In many cases, vertical mixing processes and grazing may determine whether bloom-favouring conditions actually result in a bloom or not. It is therefore imperative to a) describe vertical mixing and its impact on phytoplankton distribution and availability of nutrients, and b) describe the interaction of the grazing chain with the primary production well enough to construct reasonable HAB growth cycle models.

5.2 Operational constraints

5.2.1 Sustainability of EO-based service data provision

The longer term sustainability of an Earth Observation service relevant to algae monitoring depends on continued future access to ocean colour data of sufficient spectral, temporal and radiometric resolution, and appropriate signal/noise ratio. It further depends upon the terms of access allowed by the satellite operating authorities to a self-funding or commercial system.

The benefits gained from using EO data in the monitoring system can be regarded as sustainable and reliable since a number of satellite EO sensors are and will be operating during the next five years, which can provide operational ocean colour data and redundancy in terms of individual sensor failure. ESA's MERIS offers possibly the best sensor system in terms of flexibility and capability for improved HAB monitoring, however near-real-time access to data may be a limiting factor. Primarily the better spatial resolution (300 meters) and the number of spectral channels will make it better suited for use in coastal and fjord studies. The NASA MODIS system provides unencrypted X-band direct broadcast data and will stimulate competition and hopefully lower costs in the data supply, and stimulate the generation of useful value-added information products.

Improved sensor performances and innovative research on the methods/algorithms for the information retrieval and applications of ocean colour data for estimation of the phytoplankton distribution will contribute to improved future use of ocean colour information products in services for HAB monitoring.

This section considers option for continued use of the current SeaWiFS and future access to planned satellite systems most notably the ESA's MERIS (launch, fall 2001) and NASA's MODIS (launched 18 December 1999).

a) Current spaceborne ocean colour sensors

The current operational spaceborne ocean colour sensors are summarised in Table 5. SeaWiFS is a commercial satellite owned by Orbimage Inc, USA, with access to research usage purchased on behalf of the scientific community by NASA. The German/Indian MOS sensor has a poor repeat

cycle, but may complement other more frequent observations. The Japanese Ocean Colour Imager (OCI) was launched into an orbit ($\pm 30^\circ$ Latitude) which does not provide observation over most European waters. The Indian Ocean Colour Monitor (OCM) sensor has no onboard recording and the data are currently only received by the Indian National Remote Sensing Agency at Hyderabad. However, it is envisaged that there will be a global network of international ground stations in the future, which may also provide near real-time data access to users. For practical applications in (H)AB monitoring the orbital and data dissemination capabilities and infrastructure are the limiting factors for better and more use of ocean colour data in support of monitoring activities.

Table 5. Current spaceborne ocean colour sensors. Source: <http://www.ioccg.org/sensors/500m.html>

SENSOR	AGENCY	SATELLITE	LAUNCH DATE	SWATH (km)	RESOLUTION (m)	NUMBER OF BANDS	SPECTRAL COVERAGE (nm)
MOS	DLR (Germany)	IRS-P3 (India)	21/3/96 -	200	500	18	408-1600
SeaWiFS	NASA (USA)	Orbview-2 (USA)	01/8/97 -	2806	1100	8	402-885
OCI	NEC (Japan)	ROCSAT-1 (Taiwan)	1/99 -	690	825	6	433-12500
OCM	ISRO (India)	IRS-P4 (India)	26/5/99 -	1420	350	8	402-885
MODIS	NASA (USA)	Terra (USA)	18/12/99 -	2330	1000	36	405-14385
MISR	NASA (USA)	Terra (USA)	18/12/1999	360	250	4	446-867
OSMI	KARI (Korea)	KOMPSAT (Korea)	20/12/1999	800	850	6	400-900

Moderate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS)

The first “new generation” MODIS scanner, was launched on NASA’s Earth Sciences Enterprise “Terra” (formerly AM-1) spacecraft in December 1999. The second will be launched on “Aqua”, formerly PM-1, in 2002. The dual operation of Terra and Aqua (with descending nodes at 10:30 LST and 14:30 LST) will offer greater opportunities for observing phenomena in cloudy conditions, and possibly short-term temporal variability. The MODIS Science Team have had significant difficulties in providing high quality information products for ocean areas, however data from November 2000 to May 2001 are of good quality but a recent problem may reduce data quality.

MODIS also provides a number of advantages over SeaWiFS:

- MODIS data will direct broadcast over X-band and can be used freely for any application: the University of Dundee (the current suppliers of SeaWiFS data to DeciDe HAB project) has developed X-band reception capabilities and similar capabilities will be at a number of ESA and non-ESA ground stations world wide.
- Simultaneous observation of ocean colour (visible spectral range), temperature (SST) and atmospheric parameters (36 spectral bands fixed), will improve the accuracy of the retrieved information products.
- Extensive on-board calibration facilities.

Compared to MERIS, MODIS only has 1-km resolution and is not spectrally programmable; like MERIS it does not tilt away from the sun and so the imagery are affected by sun glint.

b) Scheduled Ocean Colour satellite sensors

There are a number of future ocean colour sensors planned (see Table 6), however the main consideration for EO data in the algae bloom monitoring system is the near-real time access to the data. In this respect the European MERIS and US MODIS sensors should offer near-real-time data access.

Table 6. Scheduled spaceborne ocean colour sensors. Source: <http://www.iocccg.org/sensors/500m.html>

SENSOR	AGENCY	SATELLITE	LAUNCH DATE	SWATH (km)	RESOLUTION (m)	NUMBER OF BANDS	SPECTRAL COVERAGE (nm)
GLI	NASDA (USA)	ADEOS-2 (Japan)	Scheduled Febr. 2002	1600	250/1000	36	375-12500
MERIS	ESA (Europe)	ENVISAT (Europe)	Scheduled October 2001	1150	300/1200	15	412-1050
POLDER-2	CNES (France)	ADEOS-2 (Japan)	Scheduled Febr. 2002	2400	6000	9	443-910
MODIS-Aqua	NASA (USA)	Aqua (EOS-PM1)	Scheduled Jan./Febr. 2002	2330	1000	36	405-14385
S-GLI	NASDA (USA)	ADEOS-3 (Japan)	Scheduled March 2006	1600	750	11	412-865
OCTS	CNSA (China)	Hai Yang-1 (China)	Scheduled Sept. 2001	1400	1100	10	402-12500

Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS)

MERIS is due for launch on ESA's Envisat satellite during fall 2001. The instrument offers significant advantages over current ocean colour satellites such as SeaWiFS including:

- Spectral bands: MERIS has 15 wavebands that can be programmed in width and location, which means that specific channels could be modified to observe specific phenomena e.g. red tides,
- Spatial resolution: MERIS has two spatial resolution modes – 300 meter regionally (Full Resolution) and 1.2 km globally (Reduced Resolution); this will mean that smaller features such as algae blooms in fjords may be detected,
- Radiometric resolution: data are digitised to 16 bits and the S/N ratios are very high (noise equivalent radiance of below $0.033 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ sr}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in the visible and 0.025 in the NIR),
- Calibration: MERIS has a number of on-board calibration mechanisms to measure potential system response degradation and wavelength stability of the sensor,
- Synergy with other instruments: the Envisat satellite will carry a suite of instruments which will enable simultaneous observation of ocean colour, sea-surface temperature, surface elevation and surface roughness, by sensors partly covering the same swath. This will enable the ocean colour biological information to be tied more closely to physical structures of the oceans.

A disadvantage of MERIS is that it does not tilt away from the sun and so images will be affected by sun glint, which may affect observation when the area of interest is on the eastern part of the

sensor swath.

MERIS data will be accessed via two main routes:

- Pre-operational research requirements are classified at Category 1 and will be supported directly from ESA User Services.
- Operational applications, so-called Category 2, will obtain data through ESA delegated “distribution entities”.

Access to EO data in near-real time is crucial for the algae monitoring service and ESA quote the delivery of Fast Delivery (FD) products at three hours for the low-resolution products; high resolution, including presumably MERIS-FR are processed on request and may take 1-3 days to deliver. Clearly the delivery of FR products in near-real time is a major challenge for the distribution entities, in order to provide information useful for services related to HAB monitoring services.

Global Imager (GLI)

GLI will be launched on Japanese ADEOS-2 in 2002 and has the following advantages over SeaWiFS:

- Has more spectral channels: 36 VIS and IR spectral channels, inclusive 15 for ocean colour
- Spatial resolution of 1km with six channels at 250m spatial resolution (including channels at 460, 545, 660 and 825 nm which could be used for monitoring coastal regions).

Compared to MERIS and MODIS the problems could be access to near-real time products.

5.2.2 Data access restriction and cost

AVHRR data have no commercial restrictions on data use and data are broadcast from the satellites. SeaWiFS data are commercial with near-real time access restricted to commercial users and scientists who have received specific authorisation for scientific NRT use from NASA. Generally there is a 14-day embargo on the scientific access to SeaWiFS data. This type of scientific NRT use is usually given in support of research cruises and field observations providing SeaWiFS calibration/validation or demonstration research projects.

In DeciDe-HAB, near-real time access to AVHRR and SeaWiFS data is provided through the NERSC web site (<http://www.nersc.no/Decide-HAB>), which is password protected to restrict access to SeaWiFS images to project users who are authorised by NASA. Only SeaWiFS Authorised Research Users are permitted to access SeaWiFS ocean colour data. The DeciDe-HAB project has been granted near-real time access to SeaWiFS data for the project period. The web-site access control system is designed so that access to specific data has to be granted as opposed to restricting access to specific data.

5.2.3 Data availability and cloud cover

Cloud cover and haze prevents use of the optical satellite sensors to observe the surface of the earth. Hence, the nominal “daily coverage” achieved over the North Sea region may in reality become significantly less. The availability of cloud free data varies significantly with season and geographic location. However, some algae blooms are associated with strong solar radiation and, hence, occur during such periods of more favourable observing conditions.

Because of erratic cloud conditions, it may be difficult to regularly monitor HAB. However, it is then important to integrate EO information from several passes (days) as well as to use this information as an initial or assimilated variable in an ecosystem modelling scheme.

5.3 Service conditions

5.3.1 Dissemination of information

a) *Early warning and regional monitoring*

In the present state of the art, EO technology is certainly an applicable information source to improve the early warning capability of some types of algae blooms. Extended *in situ* observations, in both time and space, is very costly in order to cover the waters of Norwegian interest. Even with a better density of such field observations the monitoring program might not be sufficient to assure early detection of HAB and updates of the initial model conditions for predictions of algae blooms.

The main advantage of EO-based information in this respect resides on the near real-time synoptic view of the marine coastal processes, and on the possibility of daily updated information. However, a major restriction concerns the frequency of availability of this information, due to frequent cloud cover in the Northern Europe, as well as the accuracy of the correction and retrieval algorithms.

Another contribution of EO data in an operational HAB management system concerns the regional trans-boundary aspects of monitoring of algae blooms. Physical processes in the coastal waters contribute to the development and advection of the phytoplankton. In particular, meso-scale circulation processes such as fronts, eddies and coastal currents determine when and where a particular water mass would interact with the coast and fjords. Therefore, estimates of such parameters are essential to improve the predictability and risk assessment concerning HAB. EO products can help to improve understanding and/or visualise the marine physical and biological surface structures at regional scales, and are therefore complementary to high-resolution *in situ* sampling in this respect. The EO based information may be used as a basis for a more representative and cost efficient planning of the *in situ* observation strategy.

Ocean fronts and main waters masses can be identified from the surface temperature (SST) and from ocean colour maps derived from EO sensor data. SST is certainly the most extensively used oceanographic geophysical parameter from EO sources. Requirements are met in terms of range of value, accuracy and temporal resolution for applications related to HABs, however the cloud cover is a limiting factor.

b) *Emergency situations – Identified HAB events*

Although technological development has made the use of satellite imagery very useful in HAB monitoring, there is room for improvements for the service, especially for use in emergency situations where the time aspect is essential. The bandwidth for telecommunications with ships in the field is highly variable, however technological solutions exist. In this respect it was found to be very useful to provide the EO and model information products to the personnel responsible for the field investigations. This enabled scientists in the field to optimise the sampling strategy. If in addition the locations of fish farms are included in such maps it would be possible to use in guiding emergency measures as well.

5.3.2 Requirements for NRT calibration and validation of EO-derived information

Accurate determination of bloom characteristics may only be achieved with the support of *in situ* observations. Such data are obviously required for identification of the algae species and its eventual toxicity, but also for accurate calibration and validation support of EO data. The development of an operational HAB monitoring service integrating EO data will require the improvement of the information flow between the field investigating units and the EO data experts. This will certainly

also imply the integration of *in situ* observations in the NRT analysis of the EO data in order to increase the overall quality of the information provided.

5.3.3 Forecasting and prediction

An efficient HAB monitoring service will need an operational forecasting model system. Ecosystem models capable of simulating various phases of HAB events (development and decay in particular) are available. The DeciDe-HAB project has shown that integrating EO-derived information in such models may significantly improve the capability to simulate the development and decay of HAB events.

An operational forecasting service should at least be able to routinely provide three to five days forecasts of identified HAB events. Such level of forecasts can only be obtained through state-of-the-art assimilation of *in situ* and EO observations in 3D-ecosystem models. The three partners in the DeciDe-HAB project will carry on their collaboration and efforts toward this goal, with other partners through the EU-funded HABLE project due to start by end of 2001.

5.4 Marketing and Prospects

The service developed and demonstrated through the ESA funded DeciDe-HAB project has raised the interest of a large number of people and entities, hence opening the way to a future sustainable economic activity related to the near real-time regional monitoring of algal- blooms from satellite data.

Potential users and customers of the DeciDe-HAB concept were identified and approached by several means:

- analysis of connection to the DeciDe-HAB web-site
- direct link to project-related institute and organisations
- Individuals who contacted us during the identified HAB events in spring 2000 and 2001

No intense market assessment was scheduled as a part of the project activities.

A questionnaire was sent to all approached companies and institutes that showed an interest in the project. The questionnaire (see Appendix 1) covered aspects such as the motivation and level of interest of the contacted persons, their feedback on the service and web-site of the project, their interest to see the demonstration system becoming an operational service, as well as investigations on willingness to pay for access to the project derived information. A summary of the findings collected through the questionnaire is given in Table 7.

Table 7 User appraisal as expressed in the evaluation questionnaire (see Annex 1).

Professional sectors Questions	Academic research	Governmental organisations	Industry	SME Operational users
Mode of awareness about DeciDe-HAB	Symposiums. Informed by other research institutes involved in the project	Regional co-ordination of HAB monitoring	Informed by the project partnership. Connection through AlgeInfo	Informed by the project partnership. Connection through AlgeInfo
Frequency of consultation	<i>Regular monitoring:</i> Occasionally <i>Alert:</i> daily	<i>Regular monitoring:</i> weekly <i>Alert:</i> daily	<i>Regular monitoring:</i> Occasionally <i>Alert:</i> every week	<i>Regular monitoring:</i> Occasionally <i>Alert:</i> three per week
Usefulness of information and service	Link service, Information presentation, Comments on phenomena	Global overview of the phenomenon out of area monitored routinely	Populated time series of SST and chlorophyll	Comments on phenomena, Documentation id downloadable
Weakness of the service	Remote sensing and modelling data are on different web-pages. No <i>in situ</i> data for ground truthing.	Remote sensing and modelling data are on different web-pages	Remote sensing and modelling data are on different web-pages	Lack of brief and simple explanation of the remote sensing data.
Personal use of the information	Comparison with other algorithm and with <i>in situ</i> data collected by own projects.	Handling of the <i>Chattonella</i> blooms Adjusting field sampling strategy Regional monitoring of HAB events.	Comparison with other products	Handling of the <i>Chattonella</i> blooms
Type of information used	SST, Chlorophyll, reports, links, model simulations	All	SST, Chlorophyll, reports, links, model simulations	Mainly reports, and images from time to time
Information missing	<i>In situ</i> database for validation (Taxonomy, nutrients, chlorophyll, cell counts, etc.)	Model simulation in fjords	<i>In situ</i> database	More focus on interpretation
Interest in a fully operational service	Might be	Yes	Yes	Yes
Willing to pay	No	Under negotiation for Norway	Might be if the service covers all area of interest of the company.	Willing to pay a part of the fee if the rest is supported by governmental organisations

5.4.1 Web-site access

Since April 2000, the DeciDe-HAB web-site has an average access rate of 10 connections per day during regular monitoring, however we experienced monthly maximum access with 342 visitors in March, 2001 (Figure 25).

Figure 25 Number of connections to the DeciDe-HAB web-site between April 2000 and August 2001.

The number of site-connections reached 84 on the 26 March 2001 during the very early and unexpected bloom of *Chattonella* along the coast of Norway and Sweden (Figure 26).

Figure 26 Number of connections to the DeciDe-HAB web-site during the pre-operational phase in March 2001. An unexpected bloom of *Chattonella* began during the weekend of March 24 and 25.

The connection origins are diverse: 65% of the connections come from Norway, followed by Germany, Denmark, Sweden, United States and France (Figure 27).

The first time connections to the DeciDe-HAB project site originate from three main sources:

- Internet search 45 %
- Connection through the ALGEMO “Link” web-page: 30%.
- Connection through the Nansen Center “Projects” web-page: 25%

Figure 27 Country of origin of the main connections to the DeciDe-HAB web-site. Since April 2000 about 1900 connections has been made to the site.

5.4.2 Main potential customers

According to the interest expressed from parties external to the project during the course of the demonstration periods, the following potential customers have been identified:

- Fisheries and aquaculture industry and trade organisations,
- Governmental agencies in charge of the control of food safety, protection of health, and environmental monitoring,
- Private consultancy companies, in environmental monitoring and impact study,
- Insurance companies, who have a part of their business related to aquaculture and fish farming,
- Research institutes with applied marine research activities,
- Tourism industries. In Northern Europe, the potential market related to tourism seems to have limited interest in HAB. However, this market seems to have a much larger potential for a service extended its activity on the Atlantic and Mediterranean coasts, where tourism is very sensitive to the water quality.

5.4.3 Service costs

In this section we do not intend to give a complete economic analysis of the implementation and operations costs for the EO elements of a DeciDe-HAB-type service. We only present current and nominal costs related to the purchase of analysis of satellite images for commercial activities. Since NRT provision of information is crucial for such a service, the development of a commercial activity would require the capability to ensure real-time acquisition and NRT analysis of ocean colour and SST satellite data.

A “Direct Downlink License” for access to SeaWiFS data can be purchased at Orbimage Corp. for real-time acquisition data. The license enables commercial customers to directly receive OrbView-2 data through their own high-resolution picture transmission (HRPT) antenna. A single license provides daily OrbView-2 coverage over a circular region with an approximate radius of 2,200 km,

costs USD 100.000 per year (115.000 Euro/year). Eight spectral channels of data are received at the size of about 100 MB/pass. There is no limitation in the applications and re-distribution of the data hence a tailored HAB application and service might be able to negotiate a lower licence fee for an annual single application use. There are also costs for the investments and maintenance in the receiving station and antennae as well as the daily operations of the installation. Optionally one may have an agreement with an existing ground station where the needed infrastructure exists, such as Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS) or Dundee as used in DeciDe-HAB.

Data from other ocean color sensors will also be available from a receiving station and/or an agency/vendor production line within the next year. The sensors with the most developed infrastructure for data aggregation and distribution are NASA MODIS and ESA MERIS. Since the data volumes and the processing software for these data are more complex and computer demanding, for a service like DeciDe-HAB the standard agency delivered products (Level-2) may be the most convenient information to use. According to the specifications these data products should meet the applications developed within DeciDe-HAB, however their implementation and verification needs to be done practically.

Based on the experience gained through the demonstration and pre-operational phases of the DeciDe-HAB project, it seems reasonable to consider that an operational service would be sustained by the work of one full-time research-engineer during the periods of operations (six months per year). The infrastructure used in the DeciDe-HAB project is based on what is available at the three project parties, which were combined for the project demonstration applications.

Based on the level of sophistication, automation and system development the annual cost for the operations and service development will be in the range from 200.000 to 400.000 Euro per year including a license for the access to SeaWiFS data. This would serve a geographical area larger than the one covered by the project, however regional algae experts needs to be involved in the local interpretations and integrated analysis with in situ data.

An initial investment of about the same amount would be necessary in order to purchase a HRPT receiving station as well as software and hardware for use in the service provision chain.

5.4.4 User Subscription Fees

Most of interested research institutions do not have the budget to pay for getting access to a service like the DeciDe-HAB.

The Directorate of Fisheries indicated, in a letter to the Ministry of Fisheries, that they need an allocated budget for use of EO data in HAB monitoring in the range of 400.000 NOK per year (50.000 Euro). However, the Norwegian authorities seems to put a much larger responsibility on the industry itself to fund and provide these services instead of relying on public resources and initiatives.

Some organisations and consultant companies, especially in Denmark, indicated that they might pay for a service as provided on the project web-site. However, the annual fee should not exceed a level of 5,000 Euro per year.

With a basic public funding and individual users licences one will need in the range of 30 to 70 clients to cover the cost for implementation of such a service. With an efficient marketing and contact with industry and other stakeholders involved in the coastal monitoring and aquaculture in the Nordic countries one might be able to develop such a service based on EO data and integration with numerical prediction models.

6. Summary and Conclusions

In view of the extensive and increasing coastal aquaculture activities in Norway monitoring of the algae blooms is of concern to the Norwegian fisheries authorities and the industry. The current algae monitoring service (ALGEINFO) in Norway has limited early warning capabilities. A trans-boundary monitoring approach including EO-derived environmental information has been demonstrated to contribute to achieving earlier warning of potential HAB, necessary for successful mitigation actions and efficient public control and management during emergency situations.

Potential benefits of including EO based information is identified for:

- Potential earlier warning of algae blooms
- Better integration of the regional (international) dimension of HAB events
- Improved planning and efficiency of *in situ* measurements and sampling
- Improvement of transboundary co-operation with neighbour countries, e.g., Sweden and Denmark, by providing regional information.

Furthermore, integration EO product with numerical forecast models have the potential to improve significantly quantitative assessment and predictions of the bloom transport, development and decay.

Combining EO data from similar sensors from different satellites (e.g., SeaWiFS and MODIS) may lead to improved, albeit irregular temporal/sensor sampling. Nonetheless, it is apparent that the present spaceborne sensor systems have spatio-temporal sampling capabilities that are adequate to meet the monitoring requirements for HAB. However, the dependency of cloud free conditions is a severe limiting factor with increasing importance at the high latitudes.

In this project we have identified, demonstrated and validated the benefit of using satellite Earth observation information in support of an existing decision making processes for disaster management operations, specifically the ALGEINFO HAB monitoring service. We have developed and implemented a pre-operational demonstration towards a sustainable service for harmful algae bloom monitoring and management decision support, related to the effective management of fisheries/aquaculture, public health, and ecosystem problems related to marine HABs.

The HAB monitoring and warning system has been constructed around a web-page concept. All operations, except the interpretation, have been automated in order to ensure the provision of information within three hours after the acquisition of the satellite data by the receiving station. This automation includes data decoding, processing up to level 2 (bio-geophysical parameters), extraction and mapping, and generation and updating of web-pages. The interpretation and reporting can be performed online, using a number of image-processing and information extraction tools are implemented on DeciDe-HAB web-site.

The capability of the developed system was demonstrated through to effective provision of documented useful information during two HAB events in respectively May 2000 and March 2001. During these events, we were able to monitor the bloom, providing daily information on the extension, progression and movement of the blooms, and even predict the decay of the bloom in May 2000. Significantly, the 2000 bloom was first detected by EO analysis. The Norwegian fisheries authorities have acknowledged the usefulness of the information provided by the DeciDe-HAB system and are interested in including the service in the future HAB monitoring activities, however this will require dedicated budget allocations which yet not are confirmed.

Presently, the development of the system into an operational and commercial service is limited due to the costs of accessing and maintaining the only present ocean colour sensor having the level of reliability required for the activity, namely SeaWiFS. In the future, other alternatives will be

available such as the data from MERIS and MODIS. However, the in orbit Terra-MODIS has not reached this level so far. A number of actions are foreseen in order to improve the current prototype toward an operational and commercial service. The main aspect of the proposed development is summarised in Table 8.

Table 8. Action plan for further development of the DeciDe-HAB service

Service component	Actions
Products	
Information content	Digest-maps (risk assessment map) should be generated operationally and become the main information product in the future, based on integration of information from several sources. Satellite-derived maps would still be accessible through links for advanced users and analysts.
Accuracy	The accuracy achieved so far for the SST products is sufficient for the application conducted. Chlorophyll-a products required a better accuracy in order to achieve a reliable identification and monitoring of HAB events. According to the specification and coastal zone specific algorithm, we may expect a breakthrough on this matter from the ENVISAT MERIS sensor products.
Algorithms	We may be able in the future to use indifferently SST products from AVHRR or ATSR (AATSR) sensors. Although ATSR algorithm is much more complex than the split-window method used in the processing of AVHRR data, the capability offered by ENVISAT to provide simultaneous images from AATSR and MERIS may greatly ease the interpretation of surface ocean features, and thus help in performing better analysis of certain algal bloom events. New algorithms for processing case II water (PML bright pixel algorithm, and artificial neural network) should lead to improved estimates of chlorophyll-a concentrations in coastal waters. In addition a number of new ocean colour products such as suspended sediment and yellow substances, may greatly help to analyse the biogeochemical state and origin of the water masses, with direct implications on the reduction of false alarm rate of algal bloom events.
Functioning	
Availability	SeaWiFS data are available free-of-charge for science and educational purpose to NASA authorised users. Near real-time access to SeaWiFS data has been granted to the DeciDe-HAB project through special agreement. More general utilisation of SeaWiFS derived products requires to pay a fee to sensor data owner - Orbimage Corp. It is not clear that near real-time provision might be provided by the data distributor. Therefore the DeciDe-HAB service can not be pursued on the basis of regular use of SeaWiFS ocean colour data. Other current ocean colour data, such as MODIS and OCM, have shown problem while access liability and operational use is of concern. The ESA policy regarding ENVISAT data provision and distribution will allow the continuity of the service regarding specially the provision of ocean colour data for first scientific and later operational use.
Timeliness	Calibration and validation of MERIS data will be conducted during spring and summer 2002.
Reliability	Improved reliability due to ongoing algorithm development, new sensor capability and synergy between various monitoring tools. One can expect discrimination of algal family from satellite data to be feasible in the near future (within 5 years), which should lead to better identification of algal bloom type and associated possible harmfulness. Routinely use of satellite-derived information with ecosystem models should also lead to better monitoring and hopefully forecasts of (H)AB events.

Table 8 follow-on	
Service component	Actions
Supply chain	
Distribution performance	The current DeciDe-HAB service has reached a high performance level, which is adequate for the pursued application. We would have to ensure for similar performance to be achieved with other satellite data sources and suppliers.
Automation level	According to the current level of automation, improvement can only be made on the data analysis part, as well as the production of information digest (e.g. regional risk map). Such development is nowadays limited by the accuracy of the information produced. The less accurate the information the more human input required in the analysis process.
Packaging of the information	Currently the information packaging is based on the data sources. In the future, it would be certainly recommended for the temporal aspect of the information to be the main classification criterion, while information might originate from many different sources including, <i>in situ</i> and satellite observation, and model simulation and forecasting.
Benefit	
Cost effectiveness	In the future, cost-effectiveness might only be guaranteed if remote sensing data is provided regularly and at a moderate cost level for data subscription. Multiplying the number of monitoring area may increase the number of potential customer while extending the period of operation of the service.
Competitiveness	An optimal service should focus on interpretation of algal bloom events, prediction of events and assessment of risk. This would require the integration of remote sensing, <i>in situ</i> and modelled data. Such an integrated service may result from the merging of different existing services and will require multiple knowledge. Merging services will result in decreasing possible competitiveness for the monitoring of a given region.
Customer readiness	
Awareness	The awareness about the HAB services can be improved through market prospecting and promotion. This has not been a focus activity in the frame of DeciDe-HAB because of the restricted access (SeaWiFS copyrights) of a large part of the information provided.
Acceptance	Operational authorities has accepted and endorsed the service development through the project. The next step is toward the possible funding entities - government and ministries, insurance company, aquaculture co-operatives, etc.
Customers	We foresee that the main customers of the type of service implemented in this project would be national authorities in charge of environmental, health and food-consumption issues, as well as industries such as insurance company, fisheries and aquaculture groups and possibly tourism industry.

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APPENDIX I: Survey questionnaire

Name:

Institute

Questionnaire concerning the DeciDe-HAB project

Web-site: www.nrsc.no/DeciDe-HAB

1. What is your professional activity and how does it relate to algae bloom monitoring?

2. What is the geographical area of your interest for HAB?

3. How did you be aware of the DeciDe-HAB project?

4. How often have you been connected to the DeciDe-HAB site between April and August 2000?
 daily three times a week
 once a week every two weeks
 occasionally

5. Did you find the information provided on the web site useful?

11. What additional information or features would you like to be available?

12. Will you have an interest using a future operational service based on the DeciDe-HAB concept?

13. Would you become a user of such a service if it becomes a commercial activity on the coast basis of 5000US\$/year?

APPENDIX 2: Description of the Current Levels of HAB monitoring in Norway

Two levels of activities are considered, corresponding to regular and emergency situations respectively:

a) Regular monitoring and dissemination of information – ALGEINFO

Regular monitoring of algae and harmful algae blooms (HABs) is conducted at the 27 stations along the coast (Figure 2) with a weekly sampling frequency in the main algae bloom period, from March to October, and less frequently in the typical “non-blooming” winter period. The observations include species determination and cell counts in surface layer and at the chlorophyll *a* maximum. The data are analysed within 24 hours and aggregated and reported within 3-4 days. The published information is free of charge and available via the ALGEINFO system at a web-site administrated by the Institute of Marine Research (IMR), Bergen, Norway (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>). This monitoring service is a joint effort by more than seven institutions funded through public and private (aquaculture industry, insurance, etc.) budgets. The main objective of the monitoring activities is to provide an early warning of algae blooms that may be a threat to the Norwegian coastal aquaculture industry along the entire coast of Norway, from the Swedish border in the south to the Russian border in the north.

The information at ALGEINFO consists of a map of the observation station locations indicating the situation of HAB species along the coast and a short text for clarification of the general situation and for each of five regions. During identified HAB situations more frequent updating of the public web-site as well as direct contact between management authorities and aquaculture industry in threatened areas are implemented through the contingency plan developed by the Directorate of Fisheries (FD). There are links to useful additional information from the web-site. One such link is to a web-site providing advice on the risk of shellfish toxicity (<http://www.snt.no/nytt/blaskjell/>).

Algae monitoring - The information on algae species distribution and concentrations (cell counts) reported in ALGEINFO is for all types of phytoplankton species, including potentially harmful algae blooms (HABs). Sampling, identification and quantification of algae are conducted by Norwegian state organisations (Directorate of Fisheries, the Institute of Marine Research, the Norwegian Institute for Water Research, the State Food Control Authority) and a private consultant company (OCEANOR AS). A large portion of the samples are collected at various aquaculture sites and then sent to one of the expert organisations for analysis. Through the experiences gained a network of algae experts has been built up, along the coast of Norway.

Reporting – The regular monitoring (sampling) and the reporting of data at ALGEINFO is conducted weekly from March to October at most of the stations, and every two weeks thereafter until winter, when the probability for the development of algae blooms along the Norwegian coast is negligible. A more frequent observation (three times per week) is done at the IMR station in Flødevigen. In general, it is the responsibility and interest of the aquaculture industry to keep themselves informed of the algae situation reported in ALGEINFO. It is the responsibility of the Directorate of Fisheries of Norway to communicate public information in case of identified emergency HAB situations.

Database, web-site and web-site server - All information displayed at ALGEINFO, are archived in a database on the host server. This allows information in ALGEINFO to be updated online with the help of a normal Internet browser. Updates are performed by authorised personnel via a protected web page of ALGEINFO. Updating is simple and entails online uploading of new information to the database and some simple intermediate steps which then generates a new updated display of ALGEINFO, provides links to the algae database on the home server and archives the previous data.

The authorised personnel responsible for updating information on ALGEINFO thus do not require particular expertise in networking and the Internet. Further, changes made to standard reporting routines e.g. HAB species to be described, are automatically indicated in previously archived sets of information. Links to other pages are also established using a normal web browser. The server is an Apache web server with an SQL database run on a Linux 5.2 computer (Pentium 200). The web-site structure is well suited to both include Earth observation images and give access to information products of public interest.

b) Measures during emergency harmful-algae-bloom situations

The Directorate of Fisheries (FD) in Norway has the primary responsibility for public management of harmful algae blooms (HABs) and providing warning and advice during HABs for the coastal waters of Norwegian interest. The Institute of Marine Research (IMR) is responsible for monitoring the algae situation at the shelf area and in the open-ocean waters of Norwegian interest. IMR is not the responsible organisation for coastal monitoring of HABs, which is performed directly under the FD, but supports the monitoring and gives expert advice during HAB situations. This role may be in the form of expert identification and evaluation of the possible HABs, initiation of dedicated cruise investigations, modelling of the HAB development and transport, and other supporting actions.

The Directorate of Fisheries has implemented an emergency-response plan with three-levels of action according to the HAB situation. The plan defines operational responses and lines of command and communication (on internal, national and communal levels, and to the marine aquaculture industry, fisheries authorities, the press, etc.), for each level of response. The plan also contains information about internal and external relevant expertise and experts at Norwegian institutions. Below is a summary of the emergency-response plan, as described in the document “Varslingsplan for Fiskeridirektoratet ved Krisehåndtering i Kystsonen” – “Contingency plan for FD in management of emergency situation in the coastal zone” (2000), published by the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries (revised annually).

The emergency-response plan with regard to HABs is provided for three algae situations, classified as follows:

- 1) The *normal* situation without indications of harmful algae blooms – The activities shall provide an overview of the algae situation, so that early warning of potential harmful situations can be made. ALGEINFO is instrumental for this task (see section 1).
- 2) The *critical* situation with indications of harmful algae species, but no related significant mortality of farmed fish. The plan shall provide an overview of the situation (distribution, toxicity), and all outgoing information to the press and mass media shall be co-ordinated by the Directorate of Fisheries via a designated *emergency-response group* defined in the plan document. The tasks of the group are to:
 - provide information directly to the regional directors of the Directorate of Fisheries,
 - assess the situation with help of regional directors,
 - arrange necessary field cruises with the coastal research vessels of the FD, R/V Munin, or other vessels to investigate the situation,
 - identify as quickly as possible the algae specie in question,
 - contact the Institute of Marine Research and other experts about possible need for support,
 - if necessary to inform the industry, press and public.
- 3) The *emergency* situation in which toxic or harmful algae threaten farmed and wild fish and/or other marine life in combination with a significant mortality of farmed fish – The plan is the same as for the *critical* situation, above, with the following additional measures:

- data on species specific harmful effects to farmed fish, wild fish and other organisms shall be collected,
- the need to supplement the *emergency-response group* with additional expertise shall be evaluated and implemented as necessary. A list of contact persons and organisations for this purpose exists, which also includes external expertise in EO applications (i.e., the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center),
- a command headquarter shall be set up at FD to emergency-related activities.

Following *critical* and *emergency* situations, the level of severity is officially declassified to *normal* when harmful algae have retreated or disappeared, and there are no indications for the development of new blooms. In this case the emergency-response group shall notify all partners and affected parties about the declassification of the HAB situation. The group shall also summarise damage and evaluate the handling of the situation.

Figure 28. Excerpt from the home page of ALGAEINFO (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>) from March 23, 2001 during an emergency situation (*Chattonella* bloom) showing status of HAB species as symbols and text. Closed circles indicated high algae concentrations.